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8 **Ambient (desorption/ionization) mass spectrometry methods**
9 **for pesticide testing in food: a review**

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33 **Abstract**

34 Ambient mass spectrometry refers to the family of techniques that allows ions to be
35 generated from condensed phase samples under ambient conditions and then, collected
36 and analysed by mass spectrometry. One of their key advantages rely on the ability to
37 allow the interrogation of samples with minimal to no sample workup. This feature map
38 well against the requirements of food safety testing, in particular, those related with the
39 fast determination of pesticide residues in foodstuffs. This review addresses the
40 application of different ambient ionization methods for the qualitative and
41 (semi)quantitative determination of pesticides in foods, attending to the different specific
42 methods used and their ionization mechanisms. The more popular techniques used are
43 those commercially available including Desorption Electrospray Ionization (DESI-MS),
44 direct analysis on real time (DART-MS), paper spray (PS-MS) and low-temperature
45 plasma (LTP-MS). Several applications described with ambient MS have reported limits
46 of quantitation approaching reference methods, typically based on LC-MS and generic
47 sample extraction procedures. Some of them has been combined with portable mass
48 spectrometers thus allowing “*in situ*” analysis. In addition, these techniques have the
49 ability to map surfaces (Ambient MS imaging) to unravel the distribution of the
50 agrochemicals on the crop.

51

52 **Keywords:** ambient mass spectrometry; pesticides; food; environment.

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55 **1. Introduction**

56 Pesticides are plant protection products intended for preventing, destroying, repelling or
57 mitigating any pest (harmful organism, such as insects, fungi, or weeds, among others) or
58 disease. They may also influence the life processes of plants (e.g. growth regulators,
59 nitrogen stabilizers) or preserve crops during production, storage and transport.^{1,2} Annual
60 pesticide sales in the period 2011-2016 were close to 400 000 tons of active ingredients,
61 only in the European Union (EU).³ As a consequence of this extended use, their residues
62 may be found in foodstuffs of both vegetable and animal origin, and also as pollutants in
63 the environment.^{4,5} In order to assess food safety and to reduce any risk to human and
64 animal health arising from pesticide exposure, pesticide residues have been restricted in
65 developed countries. Public organizations such as EU, the United States Environmental
66 Protection Agency (USEPA) or Codex Alimentarius have established maximum residue
67 levels (MRLs) permitted in food, taking into consideration the acceptable daily intake of
68 pesticides (amount of pesticide ingested daily during the whole life without leading to
69 noticeable adverse effect).⁶

70

71 This framework fosters the development of analytical methods enabling the detection of
72 pesticides at concentration levels below the MRLs set.⁷ Multiresidue methods, the
73 preferred option for food analysis, rely on hyphenated techniques such as gas
74 chromatography/mass spectrometry (GC-MS) or high performance liquid
75 chromatography/mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS)⁶. Nowadays, the feasibility of real-time
76 pesticide testing, performed “*in situ*”, with little or no sample preparation and avoiding
77 the chromatographic separation step, remains a challenge which focus the attention of
78 food safety researchers. This greener approach, which fulfils many Green Analytical
79 Chemistry principles, is feasible using Ambient MS techniques as captured in **Figure 1**.⁸

80

<Figure 1>

81

82 Ambient MS⁹ is a rapidly growing field started with the development of desorption
83 electrospray ionization (DESI)¹⁰ and direct analysis in real time (DART)¹¹. Since its
84 inception, over eighty different Ambient MS approaches have been proposed for high-
85 throughput testing and also for MS-imaging, being their connection the fact that analyte
86 desorption and ionization steps take place under ambient open-atmosphere conditions
87 with no (or scarce) sample workup; yet there is no consensus on classifying them¹².

88 Primary ionization mechanism is the more frequently used classification criterion,
89 breaking down ambient MS techniques into (i) those closely related to electrospray
90 ionization (ESI) and (ii) those resembling atmospheric pressure chemical ionization
91 (APCI), generally plasma-based techniques.^{13,14} Alternatively, ambient MS techniques
92 may be organized by desorption or sample processing method (*i.e.*, thermal desorption,
93 liquid extraction, use of lasers for desorption, etc)^{15,16}, and the combination of different
94 criteria leads to establish subcategories. Readers interested in fundamentals of the
95 different techniques and their classification according to the driving forces of both
96 desorption and ionization steps are referred to different general
97 reviews.^{17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25} More detailed information about a particular subcategory of
98 ambient ionization techniques may be found in specific reviews on spray-based,^{26,27}
99 plasma-based^{28,29,30} and laser-based methods.^{15,16}

100

101 This review article is focused on the application of ambient MS to pesticide residue
102 analysis in food and environmental samples. The review is broken down in two main
103 sections: ESI-related and APCI-related ambient MS methods, providing an overview of
104 different ambient desorption/ionization MS methods as well as representative examples
105 of their application to pesticide residue determination^{31,32}. The different approaches,
106 applied in the field, are presented, highlighting the advantages and limitations for their
107 application in pesticide testing.

108

109

110 **2. Electrospray-related ambient mass spectrometry methods applied to pesticide** 111 **testing**

112 In ESI-related ambient methods, the analytes are desorbed from the sample, and
113 transferred to the atmospheric pressure inlet of the MS as charged solvent microdroplets.
114 An overview of the more popular methods is represented in **Figure 2**. Selected
115 applications in pesticide residue analysis are summarized in **Table 1**.

116

< **Figure 2** >

117 **2.1 Desorption Electrospray Ionization Mass Spectrometry (DESI-MS)**

118 DESI was the first ambient ionization mass spectrometry method developed by Takats
119 and Cooks¹⁰. It is commercially available³³. In DESI experiment (**Figure 2a**), a charged

120 high-velocity spray of microdroplets is directed towards sample (condensed-phase), and
121 secondary droplets, including the species of interest, are then transferred through air to
122 the atmospheric pressure interface of a mass spectrometer where solvent evaporation
123 occurs, yielding gas-phase ionized compound(s). A solvent layer created by the initial
124 spray dissolves the compounds deposited on the surface; subsequent spray droplets
125 collide with the solvent layer, ejecting droplets containing the analyte from the surface
126 towards the MS inlet.¹⁰ More detailed discussions on DESI operation can be found in
127 selected specific reviews.^{34,35}

128

129 DESI has been applied to interrogate pesticides from both untreated crop surfaces and
130 extracts obtained from dedicated sample workup procedures (*e.g.* QuEChERS (quick,
131 easy, cheap, effective, rugged, and safe)).^{36,37} Representative agrochemicals including
132 insecticides (*e.g.* isofenphos-methyl, malathion), herbicides (*e.g.* ametryn, atrazine), and
133 fungicides (*e.g.* imazalil, prochloraz, triazoles) were detected at similar or lower
134 concentrations than MRLs set. The use of isotopically labelled internal standards (ILIS)
135 provided quantitative results in agreement with those obtained by reference methods
136 using LC-MS/MS or GC-MS.^{36,37} DESI-MS fruit peel analyses were found a useful
137 screening method to interrogate samples containing pesticide residues, either analysing
138 directly the fruit peel surface³⁶ or by rubbing the peel with a glass slide subsequently used
139 as substrate for DESI-MS.³⁷ Likewise, DESI-MS was used to determine chlorpropham
140 on potato surfaces,³⁸ dimethoate, tebuconazole, and trifloxystrobin on olive and vine
141 leaves,³⁹ and atrazine residues on Chinese cabbage leaf⁴⁰ (see **Table 1**). The main
142 limitations for quantitative analysis on surfaces are low precision and the presence of
143 matrix effects.³⁹

144 A challenging pesticide such as thiram could not be directly detected on the surface of
145 pear leaves,⁴¹ but surface extraction with acetonitrile was appropriate for DESI-MS/MS.
146 Using ILIS, semi-quantitative results could be demonstrated in spiked samples.
147 Extraction of the homogenized fruit by QuEChERS method was inappropriate, due to
148 severe suppression effects.

149 The feasibility of high-throughput *in situ* screening methods would be a convenient and
150 cost-effective approach, as the number of samples subjected to a comprehensive
151 evaluation would be significantly reduced. The combined use of ambient ionization

152 methods and portable (handheld) mass spectrometers represents an interesting option to
153 move the food control from the laboratory to the market shelves. This was first
154 demonstrated by Mulligan *et al.*⁴² using DESI to detect DEET, alachlor and atrazine in
155 leaves and vegetable surfaces with no sample treatment. Sensitivity, selectivity and rapid
156 detection could be satisfactorily achieved for the detection of target compounds in
157 relevant field of analysis. Thus, DEET on the surfaces of cornstalk leaves or tomato was
158 detected below 10 ng.

159 **< Table 1 >**

160 The implementation of ESI-related ionization sources in portable mass spectrometers for
161 *in situ* analysis of real samples is a very interesting approach that has been explored for
162 pesticide residue testing, using not only DESI but also PS techniques.^{42,43} Another
163 interesting feature explored with DESI is the development of chemical images (mass
164 spectrometry imaging (MSI)) of pesticide residues in crops (DESI-MSI). The distribution
165 of pesticides in different parts of *Cotoneaster horizontalis* and *Kalanchoe blossfeldiana*
166 was investigated by Gerbig *et al.*⁴⁴ using DESI-MSI. The distribution of contact pesticides
167 (pyrethrins, rapeseed oil, imidacloprid, and methiocarb) on the plant surface and
168 redistribution in plant stem and leaf of a systemic pesticide (dimethoate) were analyzed
169 by DESI-MSI. A mass range from m/z 300 to 1500 was acquired to detect pyrethrins and
170 triglyceride (TG) ions present in rapeseed oil. The TG showed non homogeneous
171 covering on leaf surface. Also, pyrethrins showed different distribution on leaf surface. It
172 was due to differences in polarity and size between them. When the same experiment was
173 performed using an insecticide which contains imidacloprid and methiocarb, the pesticide
174 distributions found on the leaf were distinctly more homogenous. The systemic
175 incorporation of dimethoate in a *Kalanchoe blossfeldiana* plant was studied, and
176 dimethoate was detected in the transport system of the plant at 25 days of treatment, and
177 homogeneously distributed in a leaf section after 60 days.

178

179 **2.2 Extractive Electrospray Ionization (EESI) and nanoEESI**

180 EESI was introduced for the first time by Chen *et al.*⁴⁵ (**Figure 2b**). It is based on the use
181 of two separate sprayers, one of them ($1-10 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$) nebulizes the sample solution and
182 the second one generates charged microdroplets of solvent (extractive ESI) which
183 continuously extracts the analytes from the sample solution into the solvent spray. It can

184 be also modified to allow the analysis of solid samples (through neutral desorption EESI)
185 or gas phase samples. This technique is very interesting for fast analysis of complex
186 samples, being able to detect traces of atrazine in raw urine,^{45,46} and of more than 200
187 toxicants, including pesticides, in urine, blood and stomach content or liver samples.⁴⁷

188

189 Nanoextractive electrospray ionization (nanoEESI)⁴⁸ mass spectrometry is based on the
190 use of a nanospray to generate the microdroplets (**Figure 2c**), using solvent flows in the
191 range 0.05 – 0.1 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$. This avoids the use of the sheath gas, so reducing the
192 parameters needing optimization and allowing hyphenation to portable mass
193 spectrometers. Sample contamination and memory effects are reduced by using a
194 disposable and manual sample injector. NanoEESI was applied to ambient mass analysis
195 of paraquat and β -cypermethrin in spiked farmland water.⁴⁸

196

197 **2.3 Paper spray and related methods**

198 In Paper spray (PS),⁴⁹ a piece of paper ending with a sharp point (held in front of the mass
199 spectrometer inlet) is wetted with a solvent; a high electric field applied and the capillary
200 action allow analyte transport and ionization (**Figure 2e**). Samples are loaded onto the
201 paper by direct addition (a volume below 10 μL is appropriate), or the paper can be used
202 as swab to sampling surfaces. The solvent is then applied once and mass spectra is
203 recorded continuously until the signal disappears. With regards to the actual mechanisms,
204 according to Espy et al.⁵⁰, two spray operation modes have been described in positive ion
205 PS-MS, spray mode 1, and spray mode 2 -after significant solvent depletion-. In the first
206 mode, multiple Taylor-cone jets are observed, which depends on the paper cut and the
207 solvent composition with ions from proton transfer reactions dominating the mass spectra.
208 In spray mode 2, single cone-jet and a corona discharge coincide, with electron-transfer
209 ions and radicals being observed (it is supposed mode 2 to occur always in negative ion
210 MS).

211

212 Although most PS applications have been performed with in-house built setups,⁵¹
213 commercial devices based on PS ionization (eg. VeriSprayTM PaperSpray ion source) are
214 available and have been tested for pesticide analysis in whole milk, olive oil and leek
215 homogenate.^{52,53} PS has been used for the determination of methaldehyde
216 (molluscicide)⁵⁴ and herbicides⁵⁵ in environmental waters by direct addition of a sample

217 aliquot onto the paper substrate. Acidification of the solvent favored the formation of
218 protonated molecules against sodium adduct, thus lowering LODs.⁵⁴ The use of
219 isotopically labeled IS allowed the quantification of atrazine and metolachlor in the low
220 microgram per liter range by PS-MS/MS. Complex matrices, such as soil extract⁵⁵ or fruit
221 homogenates^{55,56} showed higher limits of detection. In contrast, Guo *et al.*⁵⁷ supported
222 that wine samples directly on the paper substrate allowed better detection and
223 quantification (using ILIS) than when QuEChERS extracts were prepared. In a recent
224 study, a semi-quantitative approach based on an extraction of tomato peels, instead of the
225 whole vegetable, allowed to distinguish between stored or field samples.⁵⁸

226

227 For screening purposes, PS-MS/MS allowed the detection of fungicides present on real
228 samples by swabbing fruit peel with paper wetted with solvent, which is further used as
229 substrate.^{43,59} The spectra obtained for some citrus fruits showed the presence of imazalil
230 and thiabendazole, identified by MS/MS analysis.⁵⁹ The sampling by paper wiping shows
231 the advantage of collecting larger amount of analyte from larger surface area, so higher
232 intensities may be obtained compared to surface analysis of agrochemicals by other
233 ambient techniques such as DESI or LTP⁵⁹.

234 PS has been combined with portable mass spectrometers to perform “*in situ*” analyses,
235 including pesticide testing in food surfaces^{43,60}. Soparawalla *et al.*⁶⁰ determined
236 thiabendazole by PS-MS in oranges using commercially available lens wipes paper (pre-
237 moistened with isopropyl alcohol) to sample oranges surface and as ionization substrate.
238 Nevertheless, signals, as well as their duration were a third lower than those obtained
239 from filter paper, which was explained as consequence of the different porosity of both
240 paper substrates.⁶⁰ Indeed, the substrate plays a key role in PS-MS, and although both
241 filter^{55,60} and chromatographic paper^{49,59} have been widely used, many modifications in
242 the composition of the substrate have been proposed and are described as follows.

243 The use of a capillary emitter embedded on the paper substrate showed positive influence
244 on the sensitivity and reproducibility comparing with standard PS.⁶¹ Pu *et al.*⁶² developed
245 a method for pyrazole fungicides (penflufen, isopyrazam, fluxapyroxad, and
246 pyraclostrobin) in wine using this PS variation; 10 μL of sample with no treatment and
247 bixafen as IS. LOQs of 2 ng mL^{-1} were obtained, in compliance with the required
248 regulatory limits. Microfluidics technologies, such as photolithography and wax
249 patterning, have been also tested in order to increase sensitivity.^{63,64} Photolithography

250 produced a high background signal, but wax barriers improved sensitivity in the detection
251 of atrazine and propazine in spiked tap water, compared to standard PS.⁶³ Paraffin
252 microchannels also showed good results in pesticide analysis (atrazine, diuron and
253 methomyl) in vegetable extracts.⁶⁵

254 The chemical modification of the substrate was also tested. For instance, urea-modified
255 paper substrate improved sensitivity in negative PS-MS because it retains anions from
256 sample solution, thus reducing adduct formation⁶⁶. In positive ion mode, silica-coated
257 paper substrate improved LOQs for 7 pesticides in milk compared to commercial paper
258 substrate⁶⁷ Molecularly imprinted polymers (MIP) has been also combined with PS
259 ionization for herbicide analysis in food.⁶⁸ MIPs were directly synthesized on cellulose
260 membranes, which were loaded (with sample) by dipping on different fruit methanolic
261 extracts (apples, bananas and grapes), then, being used as PS substrate after washing and
262 drying. Remarkable selectivity and LOQs below the established MRL ($100 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) were
263 achieved for diuron and 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D), in positive and negative
264 ion mode, respectively.⁶⁸ It is also worth mentioning the use of substrate paper coated
265 with carbon nanotubes (CNTs)⁶⁹ which enabled the ionization of pesticides on orange
266 peel with low voltages -in the range of volts instead of kilovolts commonly used in PS-
267 MS-.

268 Finally, a smart and environmentally friendly modification of PS consists on the
269 replacement of the paper by a natural porous substrate, the sample itself. In this regard,
270 leaf spray (LS)⁷⁰ is a variation of the PS where the plant tissue acts simultaneously as
271 substrate, sample and ion source. In this method, the gas phase ions are generated directly
272 from the plant tissue, no other ionization device or support is needed beside the
273 application of HV and a solvent. The direct determination of agrochemicals in fruit and
274 vegetable tissues with no sample pre-treatment was demonstrated.^{65,71} Signals were
275 observed even without solvent addition, due to the presence of natural juice on fruit and
276 vegetables, but more intense signals and better signal to noise ratios were obtained by
277 adding solvent.⁷¹ LODs below EU MRLs were reported^{65,71} and discrimination between
278 organic and conventional samples was shown,⁷¹ providing also a semi-quantitative
279 estimation of the concentration of pesticides in non-organic samples by external
280 calibration. Another variation of paper spray for pesticide analysis is the wooden-tip
281 ESI,⁷² in which the porous substrate is a toothpick. The narrow-stick shape allows the
282 generation of sharp electrosprays. Sample loading can be carried out by pipetting or

283 directly dipping the wooden-tip into the sample solution. When a high voltage is applied
284 and few microliters of solvent added to the tip, spray generation takes place and analyte
285 ions are transferred to the MS. Analysis of beta-cypermethrin in spiked apple juices was
286 satisfactorily performed as a proof of principle of this approach⁷³.

287

288 **2.4 Other electrospray-based ionization methods: PESI and TD-EDI**

289 A solid needle electrospray probe for liquid samples analysis called probe electrospray
290 ionization (PEI) (**Figure 2d**) was developed by Hiraoka *et al.*⁷⁴. A small amount of
291 liquid sample is picked by the needles, with an automated movement on the vertical axis.
292 Then, the needle is positioned in front of the MS inlet and an applied HV leads to ESI of
293 the sample. PEI is free from clogging problems compared to ESI-based ion sources
294 using capillaries. This source, commercially available⁷⁵, has been applied to the
295 determination of polar pesticides (glufosinate, and paraquat) in human serum from real
296 poisoning cases^{76,77} with results consistent (using IS) to those obtained by standard
297 methods. A variant (sheath-flow probe electrospray ionization (SF-PEI))⁷⁸ using a
298 sheath liquid flow with a solid probe was applied to pesticide analysis in real-time from
299 living plant tissues. Acephate, acetamiprid and thiophanate-methyl applied to the plant
300 were detected, finding intense signals of sodium and potassium adducts together with the
301 protonated molecule. However, the presence of these adducts and the lack of
302 reproducibility in the sample amount loaded in the needle probe, prevent SF-PEI from
303 providing absolute quantification values.

304

305 A relatively similar approach was proposed by Shiea *et al.*, so called thermal desorption
306 electrospray ionization (TD-ESI-MS).⁷⁹ A metal probe is used to sample analytes; then,
307 the probe is located in a pre-heated oven (**Figure 3**), with the analytes being desorbed
308 with a nitrogen gas stream, transferred into an ESI plume to be ionized, and subsequently
309 detected by MS.

310

<Figure 3>

311 TD-ESI has been used to detect pesticide residues from the surfaces of fruit and
312 vegetables.^{80,81} The decay, distribution, and removal of pesticides from fruits and
313 vegetables surfaces by soak in water or detergent baths were studied.⁸⁰ The technique
314 was useful for the screening of pesticides, but quantitative results cannot be provided by
315 TD-ESI in solid samples due to the inhomogeneous distribution of the analytes

316 throughout the surface.^{80,81} TD-ESI has been also applied in the forensic field for the rapid
317 identification of ingested pesticides.^{82,83} A set of pesticides commonly detected in self-
318 poisoning patients in Taiwan have been analysed by TD-ESI in gastric juice and oral
319 fluid, achieving LODs in the parts per billion level (see **Table 1**). This involves a quick
320 analytical process, which allows the rapid identification of pesticides before they reach
321 the blood stream in self-poisoning patients, thus offering a promising tool for point-of-
322 care based on ambient mass spectrometry.

323

324 **3. Atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI)-related ambient mass** 325 **spectrometry methods applied to pesticide testing**

326 APCI-related ambient MS methods include those which use an electric discharge to
327 generate the species responsible for analyte ionization. Analyte ions are formed through
328 series of gas-phase ion-molecule reactions with environment reagent species produced by
329 a type of discharge. Additionally, in plasma-based techniques, ionization is also produced
330 by energy-transfer reactions between the activated reagent species (e.g., helium
331 metastables) and the analyte molecules.¹⁴ Positive ionization is mainly attributed to
332 Penning ionization and proton transfer from water cluster ions, whereas a variety of
333 mechanisms such as electron capture and anion attachment, have been proposed for
334 negative ionization.⁸⁴

335 In these ionization sources, a gas flow (*e.g.* He, N₂ or air) is excited by an electrical
336 discharge produced between two electrodes by applying either a direct-current (DC) or
337 an alternating-current (AC) voltage at frequencies from kilohertz to several megahertz.
338 Here, APCI-related ionization sources are sorted out in three groups, according to the
339 featured discharge: a) glow discharge (GD) which is generated by DC voltages
340 originating currents from hundreds of microamperes to several milliamperes and heating
341 of the plasma gas; b) corona discharge (CD) which is produced around the tip of a needle
342 electrode by DC supply and generates currents in the low microampere range; and c)
343 dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) which is generated by an AC supply between two
344 electrodes separated for at least one dielectric layer, providing a plasma close to room
345 temperature and currents in the microampere range. For details about the fundamentals
346 of plasma physics the readers are referred to specific literature.⁸⁵ Schematic
347 representations of APCI-related ionization sources following discussed are shown in

348 **Figure 4** and **Figure 5**. A summary of different methods developed for pesticide analysis
349 using these sources is shown in **Table 2**.⁸⁷⁻¹⁴¹

350 < **Figure 4** > and < **Table 2** >

351

352 **3.1 Plasma sources based on an atmospheric pressure glow discharges (APGD)**

353 **3.1.1 Direct Analysis on Real Time (DART)**

354 DART is a commercially available ionization source⁸⁶ and probably the more extended
355 ambient MS method for pesticide residue testing, first described by Cody *et al.*¹¹ It
356 consists of a tube divided in different chambers through which a gas (typically N₂ or He)
357 is flowing through. A DC corona-to-glow discharge in the first chamber induces the
358 formation of electrons, excited-state species and ions.²⁸ The gas flows through one or
359 two chambers that can be used to filter ions and to heat the discharge gas before it
360 impinges the sample placed near the atmospheric pressure inlet of the MS instrument
361 (**Figure 4a**).

362

363 A set of different sampling assemblies have been also developed together with DART
364 including the, so called, transmission mode DART (TM-DART)⁸⁶, and different
365 autosamplers and pipette-based devices for sampling solid, liquid or gas samples. Thus,
366 strobilurin fungicides residues were determined in wheat samples by Schurek *et al.*⁸⁷ by
367 DART- TOF-MS. The utility of DART-TOFMS method for a rapid qualitative screening
368 of the target fungicides in wheat grains without sample preparation requirements was
369 attempted at concentration levels close or higher than the established MRLs. For
370 quantitative purposes, the extraction of pesticides was carried out with ethyl acetate prior
371 to DART-TOFMS analysis. The obtained LOQs (ranging 5 to 30 µg kg⁻¹) were lower than
372 MRLs, and approached the results obtained by conventional LC-MS/MS using
373 QuEChERS extraction.

374 The same group also showed the applicability of this methodology for the analysis of two
375 dithiocarbamate fungicides (thiram and ziram) in pears.⁴¹ Solvent extraction of the fruit
376 surface with acetonitrile was preferred to QuEChERS procedure. The obtained LOQs
377 comply with the EU-MRLs of fruit crops, and quantitative analysis was possible using

378 ILIS. These results were compared to surface analysis of fruits by DESI-MS/MS, which
379 was suitable for thiram but not for ziram.

380 DART-Q-TOF-MS/MS was used in a collaborative study of Zhang and Dong⁸⁸ for the
381 confirmation and quantification of dicyandiamide in powdered milk, using simple
382 extraction with a mixture of water and acetonitrile. Quantitative analyses were performed
383 with a high reproducibility without ILIS (commonly used to correct fluctuations in the
384 desorption step) using TM-DART (**Figure 4b**). The results showed that TM-DART was
385 useful for semi-quantitative analysis of pesticides in insecticide-treated nets at
386 concentration levels lower than $0.5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ (10 ng) of deltamethrin, using either He or N₂
387 as discharge gas. The use of a fixed geometry eliminated the need of sample position
388 optimization.

389 Zhang and Dong also reported that TM-DART provided enhanced precision compared to
390 other sampling devices for the determination of pesticide residues in wine samples.^{89,90}
391 Quantitative analysis of the targeted pesticides was performed with a triple quadrupole
392 instrument operated in multiple reaction monitoring mode. Direct determination of
393 pesticides in red or white wine was achieved in 3 min with LOQs ranging from 25 to 500
394 ng mL⁻¹. However, QuEChERS treatment was found useful to minimize matrix effects
395 and improve sensitivity (for 31 out of 50 pesticides) and LOQs (decreased up to 1-100 ng
396 mL⁻¹).⁹⁰ Likewise, Lara *et al.*⁹¹ also implemented the use of the Quick Polar Pesticide
397 Extraction (QuPPE) method⁹² with an additional clean up step in order to enable the
398 determination of a group of polar pesticides in lettuce and celery by DART coupled to
399 HRMS.

400 The use of foam swabs wetted with a solvent as sampling method on surfaces of fruits
401 and vegetables has been tested. Polyurethane foam swabs were proven to be effective for
402 the analysis of pesticide mixtures containing over two hundred species.^{93,94,95} A
403 temperature gradient in the DART gas heater allowed the detection of such a great number
404 of pesticides in a 3-min run. Cotton and polyester cleaning swabs were also useful⁹⁶
405 although polyester swabs have the disadvantage that its “background” ions itself
406 dominate the spectrum.

407 Desorption temperature provided by the gas heater is one of the most critical analyte-
408 dependent factors to be optimized, since it must be compatible with the sampling method

409 (i.e. not degrading swabs or solid substrates) while providing effective desorption with
410 high signal (which may include thermally labile compounds).

411

412 Solid-phase microextraction (SPME) has been combined with DART for analyte
413 preconcentration and reduction of matrix effects for liquid samples. Wang *et al.*⁹⁷
414 analyzed triazine herbicides in lake water and orange juice by coupling of in-tube SPME
415 (IT-SPME) with DART-MS. IT-SPME is based on the use of a carbon-nanotubes-
416 incorporated polymer monolith and the online analyte desorption by the DART-MS
417 system, leading to analyte desorption and ionization. Method precision was improved
418 using an ILIS, and LOQs ranged from 0.06 to 0.46 ng mL⁻¹. The direct hyphenation of
419 SPME to TM-DART (SPME-TM-DART) was introduced by Gómez-Ríos and
420 Pawliszyn,⁹⁸ based on a metallic mesh coated with adsorbent particles which extracts the
421 target analytes. SPME-TM DART devices were used for screening and quantification of
422 pesticides in food (grape juice, orange juice, and cow milk) and environmental matrices
423 (river water).⁹⁹ The total analysis time did not exceed 2 min per sample with LOQs in the
424 range 0.1 – 5 µg kg⁻¹.

425

426 Therefore, to some extent, the analysis of pesticide residues in complex samples by
427 DART-MS, and also by most of the ambient MS methods described, requires some
428 sample treatment in order to reduce matrix effects to achieve both LOQs complying with
429 the stringent regulations and to improve precision. Notably, some approaches that utilize
430 minimal sample manipulation (e.g. surface extraction, SPME) give satisfactory
431 quantitative results, particularly when ILIS are used.

432

433 **3.1.2 Flowing atmospheric-pressure afterglow (FAPA)**

434 Andrade *et al.*¹⁰⁰ proposed the use of the flowing afterglow (FA) of an APGD (first named
435 FA-APGD and later FAPA) for the soft ionization of molecules. Like in DART, the
436 discharge is not directly in contact with the sample. The reagent species are formed
437 through the interaction of the ambient air with the excited species from the discharge and
438 are transported outside the discharge chamber (see **Figure 4h**), which is mounted in a
439 Teflon body into which typically He flows. As a consequence of the generated GD, the

440 gas is heated (even above 200 °C) by collisions with electrons, so no additional heating
441 is required for sample desorption.¹⁰⁰

442 For instance, thiabendazole was detected on lemon skin by wiping the surface with a swab
443 and exposing it to FAPA.¹⁰¹ The direct exposure of apple skin spiked with a mixture of
444 pesticides (alachlor, atrazine, carbendazim, carbofuran, dinoseb, isoproturon,
445 metolachlor, metolcarb, propoxur, and simazine) yielded LODs in the range 0.01 – 2.0
446 ng g⁻¹, below the MRLs set by the EU for the entire crop (in the range 50-100 ng g⁻¹).¹⁰²
447 Trace analysis of pesticides in spiked fruit juices from apple, cranberry, grape, and orange
448 were performed pipetting 1 µL of the juice into pieces of filter paper subsequently
449 exposed to the afterglow. A hybrid Q-TOF was used, but the response of spiked fruit
450 juices at different concentrations was not linear and the precision was around 20%. A
451 standardized method for sample positioning, together with the use of ILIS may solve the
452 problems associated to reproducibility.

453 Shelley *et al.*¹⁰³ developed an improved design of the FAPA source (**Figure 4h**) leading
454 to background signal reduction in both positive and negative ionization modes (89% and
455 99%, respectively), and, in addition, the capillary anode reduced the quantity of atomic
456 oxygen (responsible of analytes oxidation in the pin-to-plate configuration). LODs
457 obtained were *ca.* one order of magnitude better than related plasma-based methods.

458 An approach, conceptually similar to FAPA, that has been also reported for pesticide
459 testing is microfabricated glow discharge plasma (MFGDP). It consists of a small planar
460 ceramic chamber with DC voltage applied between two plate electrodes.¹⁰⁴ It features
461 lower gas temperatures than FAPA. Semi-quantitative analysis of pesticides was
462 performed with QuEChERS extracts of fruits and vegetables by MFGDP-MS/MS.¹⁰⁵ The
463 solutions were spotted onto a filter paper and exposed to the plasma, achieving LODs
464 between 0.13 and 3.1 ng g⁻¹ and linearity up to two orders of magnitude.

465

466 **3.2 Ambient mass spectrometry methods based on corona discharge ionization**

467 Amongst these methods, Desorption Atmospheric Pressure Chemical Ionization (DAPCI)
468 ^{106,107} (**Figure 5a**) is based on the same principle as APCI. A corona discharge is
469 generated on the tip of the sharp needle (by applying a DC voltage of few kV), and reagent
470 species are subsequently generated in its surrounding environment. Both gases and liquid
471 solvents (introduced through an evaporation chamber) may be used to form reagent ions.

472 DAPCI has shown excellent results for detection of different drugs and biological
473 samples,^{108,109} with signal improvement compared with both DART and DESI. As an
474 example, signals for cinchocaine and hydrocortisone (the main ingredients of an analysed
475 ointment) were 5 and 50-fold higher with DAPCI than with DESI.¹⁰⁸ Chen *et al.*¹¹⁰ used
476 DAPCI to detect picograms of atrazine directly on unripe pumpkin surface and in cloths.
477 MS/MS analyses together with chlorine isotope pattern were used to confirm the presence
478 of the herbicide.

479

< Figure 5 >

480 Besides DAPCI, other corona-based ambient MS methods are also shown in **Figure 5**.
481 Thermal dissociation atmospheric chemical ionization (TDCI) was developed in 2011 by
482 Han *et al.*¹¹¹. Ionic liquids (green solvents) are used to produce reagent ions by thermal
483 dissociation processes; these reagent ions interact with the analytes of the raw samples
484 yielding analyte ions that are transferred to the MS. The original design of this source
485 included two electrode plates assembled in a 90-degree configuration in front of the MS
486 inlet and a heatable sample holder (see **Figure 5b**). The detection of both polar and
487 nonpolar (nonvolatile) compounds was demonstrated.¹¹¹ A second design was used by
488 Ouyang *et al.*¹¹² for dimethoate in orange juices, achieving a low LOQ ($0.9 \text{ pg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) with
489 no sample workup. Nevertheless, the authors reported some constraints of the technique
490 due to the use of ILs, such as the possible contamination of the ion source with the
491 continued use of these solvents and their high proton affinity, which hinders its
492 application.

493

494 Another corona-based approach described by Wang *et al.*¹¹³ is desorption corona beam
495 ionization (DCBI) (**Figure 5d**). It has similarities with DART source, such as the use of
496 He (discharge gas) and the need of heating the gas for sample desorption. DCBI source
497 produces a visible corona beam, allowing sampling area localization, thus being useful
498 for imaging/surface experiments. In addition, it also allows gradient temperature
499 operation, which permits sequential sample desorption to achieve a rough separation of
500 analytes from complex mixtures. Pesticides were studied using this source, achieving
501 absolute LODs ranging between 1 to 9.6 ng. In order to avoid sampling difficulties in
502 liquid or gaseous matrices, the use of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) was also proposed
503 as sampling substrate (by immersion in water)¹¹⁴. An improvement in LODs ($1 \text{ }\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)

504 for pesticide (acephate, isoprocarb, dimethoate, dichlorvos, and dicofol) detection in
505 water, together with an increase in the number of identifiable compounds were achieved.
506 Likewise, other improvements were proposed by Wang *et al.*¹¹⁵ based on room
507 temperature ionic liquids (RTILs) matrix-assisted DCBI.

508

509 **3.3 Ambient mass spectrometry methods based on dielectric barrier discharge**

510 Dielectric barrier discharges (DBDs) are widely used for plasma generation, because they
511 offer some attractive features such as stable operation at atmospheric pressure, small size,
512 low power consumption and a cold plasma production.²⁸ Several designs of DBDs have
513 been proposed for Ambient MS including one or two dielectric barriers between the
514 electrodes.^{116,117} Amongst them, low-temperature plasma (LTP)¹¹⁸ and the so-called
515 DBDI^{119,120} have been used and compared for pesticide residue testing. LTP is based on
516 a ring-to-pin configuration and one dielectric barrier, whereas DBDI is based on a ring-
517 to-ring configuration. Na *et al.*¹²¹ reported the first ambient DBDI source (**Figure 4c**). It
518 was a pin to plate configuration composed by a discharge needle (a hollow stainless-steel
519 needle) and a copper sheet electrode, both separated by a glass slide acting as dielectric
520 barrier and sample substrate. By applying an alternating voltage, a stable low-temperature
521 plasma is formed between the discharge electrode and the glass surface²⁸ and the analytes
522 (located on the glass slide) are desorbed and directly introduced into the MS. This initial
523 configuration (pin-to-plate) was followed by LTP (pin-to-ring) and DBDI (ring-to-ring)

524 **3.3.1 Dielectric Barrier Discharge Ionization (DBDI) (ring-to-ring)**

525 This configuration consists of a glass capillary of small dimensions surrounded by two
526 outer ring electrodes. The plasma jet dimensions depends on the gas flow (0.1 – 0.25 L
527 min⁻¹), and cover a few millimeters.¹¹⁹ The back electrode is grounded, while an AC
528 high voltage is applied to the front electrode (closer to the MS inlet) with all the system
529 being isolated with a Teflon casing. This probe was primarily utilized as ionization source
530 for both ion mobility spectrometry¹²² and LC-MS by Franzke and coworkers,¹²⁰ but also
531 applications were performed for ambient MS analysis of pesticides. Gilbert-López *et*
532 *al.*¹²³ proposed the combination of desorption by a continuous wave near-infrared diode
533 laser with subsequent ionization by DBDI probe (LD-DBDI) as an ambient ionization
534 method for detection of non-volatile chemicals on surfaces by MS (**Figure 4d**). A group
535 of non-volatile pesticides (spinosad, prochloraz, and propazine) and other molecules with
536 low vapor pressure were selected as analytes. The approach was applied to solvent

537 standards and fragment confirmatory ions were obtained along with the protonated
538 molecules of the studied pesticides. The results obtained by LD-DBDI-MS were distinctly
539 superior to those obtained by thermal-assisted desorption.¹²³

540 **3.3.2 Active capillary plasma ionization (ACaPI)**

541 The active capillary source designed by Zenobi *et al.* consists of a quartz capillary
542 connected directly to the MS inlet, and the desorbed molecules are ionized in the gas
543 phase during ion transfer into the vacuum. Different configurations have been tested for
544 the electrodes,¹²⁴ and in the final design the DBD discharge occurs between an outer ring
545 electrode connected to an AC high voltage and an inner ring grounded electrode (**Figure**
546 **4e**). This source has been recently commercialized under SICRIT® acronym (Soft
547 Ionization by Chemical Reaction in Transfer).¹²⁵ In contrast to the ring-to ring
548 DBDI^{120,122}, in ACaPI source the analytes flow through the capillary into which the
549 discharge is produced, and are in contact with the grounded electrode. N₂ is usually
550 employed as discharge gas in ACaPI, although regular air (doped with a low percentage
551 of humidity) may be also used¹²⁶.

552 Ambient MS applications of ACaPI source include the analysis of the pesticide
553 dichlorvos, by a handheld mass spectrometer.¹²⁷ Pesticide testing using ACaPI source
554 involves so far, the use of hyphenated LC-MS or GC-MS techniques¹²⁶, or the use of
555 solid-phase microextraction (SPME)¹²⁸ with the SPME fibers used as substrate for
556 subsequent thermal desorption and analyte ionization.

557

558 **3.3.3 Low Temperature Plasma (LTP)**

559 LTP probe was developed by Harper *et al.*¹¹⁸ using a glass capillary of higher dimensions
560 than that used in DBDI^{120,122}. A stainless-steel grounded pin electrode axially centered
561 inside the capillary and a copper outer HV electrode located in the opposite extreme of
562 the tube generate a dielectric barrier discharge induced by an AC voltage. The inverse
563 electrode configuration has been also described (inverse LTP)¹²⁹. He and N₂ are
564 commonly used as discharge gases, and the plasma jet formed interacts with the sample,
565 prompting the desorption and ionization of molecules located on the surface (**Figure 4f**).
566 Amongst the different LTP assemblies used, it is worth to mention a miniaturized version
567 of LTP (glass capillary of 40 mm x 1.0 mm i.d., 1.6 mm o.d.) reported recently and applied
568 to the analysis of gases or aerosols¹³⁰ and a 3D-printed holder design¹³¹ with the aim of

569 providing a reproducible model for LTP probes construction with potential application in
570 MS imaging.

571 The first thorough study of LTP-MS applied to pesticide testing in fruit extracts deposited
572 over a glass surface and fruit peels was performed by Wiley *et al.*¹³². Notably, the peak
573 signal in LTP experiments was distinctly enhanced when the substrate was heated^{118, 132}.
574 LODs in the range from 0.2 to 200 ng g⁻¹ were obtained for pesticides in spiked
575 QuEChERS extracts of pepper, tomato and orange using LTP-MS/MS with heated
576 substrate at *ca.* 100°C.¹³² With a high-resolution Orbitrap MS instrument, LOQs in the
577 range 1-7 ng g⁻¹ were obtained for a group of pesticides in grape and raspberry
578 QuEChERS extracts, distinctly below the MRLs.¹³³ Moreover, some authors have
579 reported successful results in the direct analysis of samples without pretreatment. As an
580 example, simple dilution applied to wines was enough to obtain LODs between 15 and
581 300 ng mL⁻¹ for ten fungicides by LTP-MS/MS using an ion trap mass spectrometer.¹³⁴
582 These values fulfilled the established MRL values, highlighting the usefulness of LTP-
583 MS for the qualitative analysis of real samples with no sample treatment.

584 Wang *et al.*¹³⁵ named thermal desorption LTP (TD-LTP) a coupling between a thermal
585 desorption sample injector and an LTP probe. A PTFE swab is used to wipe out a solid
586 sample surface, or it is wetted by a liquid sample or extract, and finally the swab is
587 inserted into the TD module. The desorbed molecules are transported by an air current
588 into the LTP plasma jet, which interacts only with sample in gas phase, originating an
589 increase in sensitivity and stability comparing with conventional LTP. TD-LTP was used
590 for the detection of 12 pesticides in broomcorn, using an ultrasound-assisted extraction
591 with methanol and the extract was deposited on a PTFE swab prior TD-LTP-MS analysis.
592 LODs ranging between 0.01 and 1 µg mL⁻¹ for solvent standards.¹³⁵

593 A different approach, proposed by Usmanov *et al.*¹³⁶, studied the desorption of low-
594 volatility compounds by liquid-solid friction. Microdroplets (*ca.* 30 µm diameter) of
595 water/methanol (1:1) were produced by a piezoelectric generator and spotted on the flat
596 surface of an ultrasonically vibrating blade (**Figure 4g**); microdroplet cavitation at the
597 hitting interface was supposed to be the cause of the neutral desorption of the analytes.
598 The vaporized analytes were subsequently ionized by a modified LTP quartz capillary
599 probe in which the pin electrode extends outside the capillary, so the plasma jet is cut off.
600 The analytes gave strong signals, which are not observed when either the blade vibrator

601 or the piezoelectric microdroplet generator were off. LODs ranged from 0.1 to 100 ng
602 (**Table 2**).

603 One of the most attractive features of ambient ionization sources is the possibility to
604 perform “*in situ*” analysis. The combination of LTP with a portable MS has been proven
605 useful as a high throughput screening method to differentiate between organic and non-
606 organic apples.⁶⁰ Wiley *et al.*¹³⁷ developed a handheld LTP source powered by a small
607 battery and either helium or compressed air were used as discharge gases. As expected,
608 helium provided better LODs than air. Despite the reduction of gas and power
609 consumption, the handheld source showed similar or slightly better analytical
610 performance than the standard LTP, LODs, ranged between 0.001 to 0.9 ng, increasing up
611 to 0.1 - 200 ng when a portable mini-MS was used.

612

613 **3.4 Desorption atmospheric pressure photoionization (DAPPI)**

614 DAPPI was developed by Haapala *et al.*¹³⁸ for rapid surface analysis of compounds with
615 a wide range of polarities (from polar to nonpolar analytes) (**Figure 5c**).¹³⁹ It involves the
616 use of a heated nebulizer microchip, which supply a heated jet of vaporized solvent, and
617 a photoionization lamp. Sample spots on a surface are desorbed by the solvent jet, which
618 is focused to the surface, subsequently, the analytes are ionized by APPI processes, and
619 finally, they are detected by the MS. Luosujärvi *et al.*¹⁴⁰ studied species commonly found
620 in environmental or food samples, including PAHs and pesticides (aldicarb, carbofuran,
621 ditalimfos, imazalil, methiocarb, methomyl, oxamyl, pirimicarb, and thiabendazole).
622 Three different spray solvents (with APPI dopants) were used in positive (acetone and
623 toluene) and negative (anisole) ion mode. LODs for the studied pesticides ranged from
624 30 to 300 pg (corresponding to 0.14 to 1.4 pmol). Orange peel was directly analysed
625 cutting a small slice and attaching it onto the sample substrate; an abundant ion at *m/z*
626 297, corresponding to protonated ion of imazalil, was observed and confirmed by
627 MS/MS.

628 Vaikkinen *et al.*¹⁴¹ compared the use of DAPPI and DESI to analyze neonicotinoid
629 compounds (thiacloprid, acetamiprid, clothianidin, imidacloprid, and thiamethoxam).
630 DAPPI gave signal-to-noise ratios from 2 to 11 times better than DESI. LODs ranged
631 from 0.4 to 5.0 fmol for neat standard solutions. DAPPI was also used to detect thiacloprid

632 on fresh rose leaves and turnip rape flowers. Analysis of plant material was performed by
633 DAPPI with no further requirements of extraction or sample preparation.

634

635 **4. Concluding remarks and future perspectives**

636 The application of ambient desorption/ionization MS methods for the determination of
637 different pesticides in foodstuffs have been extensively studied in recent years. One of
638 the major attractive features of ambient MS sources is the possibility of direct analyte
639 determination on sample surfaces (*i.e.* determination of contact pesticides on crops). The
640 first consequence of real-time surface analysis of trace amounts of organic compounds is
641 the ability to map chemicals on surfaces, and eventually, the acquisition of chemical
642 images with moderate lateral resolution, which might be highly informative, for instance,
643 to understand the application of agrochemicals on crops and their mechanisms
644 (degradation, persistence, distribution, ...). For instance, the use of DESI for MS
645 imaging⁴⁴ or the the combination of laser ablation with FAPA-MS¹⁴² and LTP-MS¹⁴³ may
646 be cited as examples of this feature.

647

648 In contrast, three main limitations may be observed for direct determination on foodstuffs
649 with ambient MS methods. Firstly, direct surface analysis is affected by the
650 nonhomogeneous pesticide distribution on the sample surface, which makes
651 quantification efforts and method validation highly challenging. Secondly, in most
652 ambient MS methods, only a small portion of the surface is interrogated so the analysis
653 may not achieve the requested detection levels (MRLs values, normally provided in
654 mg·kg⁻¹ for the whole crop) depending on the interrogated surface (sweet spot effect).
655 These limitations are usually avoided by the use of extraction techniques, such as surface
656 liquid extraction, the use of dedicated procedures such as QuEChERS procedure, or
657 sampling the targeted surface with swabs, paper or foam disks wetted with an appropriate
658 mixture of solvents, with the subsequent determination directly on the sampling substrate
659 by an ambient MS method. A relatively low portion of the literature address the
660 quantitative analysis at low concentration levels, for instance with the use of ILIS. This
661 issue yet remains as one of the main challenges to solve given the lack of homogeneity in
662 the distribution of the pesticides in the sample. Thirdly, the occurrence of matrix effects
663 in quantitative ambient MS methods should not be overlooked. There is a lack of thorough
664 evaluation of matrix effects, although some studies have addressed this aspect.¹⁴⁴

665 Finally, one of the most attractive features of ambient ionization sources is their use in
666 portable mass spectrometers to perform *in situ* analysis. Amongst the ionization sources
667 that has been coupled to a portable mass spectrometer we should mention DESI⁴², PS⁶⁰,
668 LTP¹³⁷ and ACaPI¹²⁷. This is, definitely one of the most promising venues where ambient
669 MS is expected to grow, as the availability of reliable portable MS instruments increases⁸.

670

671 **Acknowledgements**

672 The authors acknowledge funding from Consejería de Economía, Conocimiento,
673 Empresas y Universidad, Regional Government of Andalucía, Spain (Project Ref.
674 RTA2018-1211) partially supported by EU FEDER funds. The authors also acknowledge
675 funding the Research Programme of the University of Jaen (Plan 2019-2020, Research
676 programme “Acción 10”). This contribution has also received funding from the European
677 Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie
678 (MSCA) grant agreement number 840743.

679

Table 1. Summary of relevant methods for pesticides analysis by ESI-related ambient mass spectrometry.

Compounds	Matrix	Ambient ionization technique/ spray solvent	Sample preparation	MS analysis	Analytical performance/matrix	Ref.
DESI						
16 pesticides	(i) Fruit or vegetable extracts; (ii) Fruit peels	DESI (4.5 kV, 5 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$), ACN/water (8:2) (1% FA)	Two approaches: (i) QuEChERS; (ii) direct peel analysis	LIT-MS/MS	LODs 1 - 90 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ in extracts	36
17 pesticides	Fruits (mango, papaya, passion fruit, apple and strawberry), and honey	DESI (3.5 kV, 125 $\mu\text{m/s}$), ACN/water (4:1) (0.1% FA)	Two approaches: (i) QuEChERS, and (ii) on fruit surface	Orbitrap MS	LODs ($\text{pg}\cdot\text{mm}^{-2}$): 1, on Teflon; 33 on apple peel	37
Chlorpropham	Potato surface	DESI (5 kV, 0.5 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$), methanol/water (1:1) (1% acetic acid)	Not required	IT-MS/MS	LOD: 6.5 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$	38
Dimethoate, tebuconazole, and trifloxystrobin	Olive and vine leaves	DESI (5.5 kV, 1 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$), methanol/water (8:2) (10 mM FA)	Not required	QTRAP-MS/MS	LOQ (ng): Dimethoate (50), tebuconazole (150), and trifloxystrobin (60)	39
Atrazine	Chinese cabbage leaf	DESI (4.5 kV, 4 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$), ACN/water (1:1) (0.1% FA)	Not required	IT-MS/MS	LOQ < 63.13 $\text{pg}\cdot\text{mm}^{-2}$	40
Dithiocarbamate fungicides: thiram and ziram	Fruit	DESI (5 kV, 5 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$), methanol/water (1:1) (0.1% FA and 10 mM ammonium formate)	Surface extraction with acetonitrile	LIT-MS/MS	LCL: thiram, 1 mg kg^{-1} ; ziram, not detected	41
Alachlor, and atrazine and DEET	Leaf and vegetable surfaces	DESI, methanol/water (1:1)	Not required	Portable IT-MS	10 ng of DEET detected on cornstalk leaf	42
Insecticides: Dimethoate, imidacloprid, methiocarb, pyrethrins, and rapeseed oil,	Plant stem and leaves	DESI-MSI (3.5 – 4 kV, 2.5 – 3 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$), mixtures of methanol/water (containing FA, $(\text{NH}_4)\text{HCO}_3$ and NaHCO_3)	Cryosectioning to study the pesticide incorporation into the plant	Orbitrap-MS	Not available	44

EESI						
Atrazine	Spiked urine (2 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$)	EESI (5 kV, 5 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$), methanol/water/acetic acid (5:5:1)	Not required	LIT-MS/MS	LOD: 0.4 fg atrazine	46
204 toxicants, including 47 pesticides	Urine, blood, stomach content, liver	EESI (4 kV, 5 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$),	Dilution and centrifugation (when needed)	LIT-MS/MS	LOD 0.002–0.09 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	47
β -cypermethrin and paraquat	Spiked farmland water	nanoEESI (5 kV, 0.05 – 0.1 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$) with methanol/water (1:1)	Not required	LIT-MS/MS	LODs ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$): β -cypermethrin (6), and paraquat (10)	48
Paper Spray (PS) and related methods						
Atrazine, boscalid, clothianidin, diphenylamine, imidacloprid and thiamethoxam	Whole milk, olive oil, and leek homogenate	VeriSpray ⁵² Paper Spray system (3.8 kV), methanol:water (9:1) (0.1% FA)	Not required/ leek homogenization in a blender followed by solvent addition (1 mg μL^{-1})	QqQ-MS/MS	Calibration curves from the low $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (1-25) to the low mg L^{-1} (25-50) in milk and olive oil, and from 20 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ to 10 mg kg^{-1} in leek homogenate	53
Methaldehyde	Environmental water	Paper spray (3.5 kV), methanol/water (0.1% FA) (1:1)	Not required. Only filtration	LIT-MS/MS	LOD: 0.05 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	54
Atrazine, propazine, and metolachlor	Ground water, lake water, soil extracts, and crop extracts	Paper spray (3.5 kV), ACN	Soil and crop extracts by solid-liquid extraction with a mixture of acetonitrile/water (80:20, v/v)	IT-MS/MS	LODs in surface water: atrazine, 3.53 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; metolachlor, 1.70 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	55
Aldicarb, imazalil, methiocarb, methomyl and thiabendazole	Oranges, grapefruits, lemons, limes, mandarins, tomatoes, apples, pears, strawberries, grapes, and sweet peppers	Paper spray (3.2 kV), H ₂ O (0.1% FA)/ACN (2:8)	Two sampling approaches: (i) wiping with the paper; (ii) samples homogenized with acetonitrile	QqQ-MS/MS	LODs < 5 mg kg^{-1} in homogenates of orange, tomato and grapes	56

36 pesticides	Red wine	Paper spray (3.5 kV), methanol or ACN	(i) Off-line QuEChERS; and (ii) On-line Paper- Adsorption	QqQ-MS/MS	LOQs: (i) 0.3-375.5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (23 analytes); (ii) ACN as spray solvent: 0.6-272.9 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (34 analytes); MeOH as spray solvent: 0.9-280.4 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (31 analytes)	57
Acephate, chlorpyrifos, and cyazofamid	Tomato peels	Paper spray (4.0 kV), methanol (0.1% FA)	Remove the peel of the tomato and perform an extraction with ACN, or water (acephate)	IT-MS/MS	LOQs: 30 ppb	58
Imazalil and thiabendazole	Peel of lemon	Paper spray (4.5 kV), methanol/water (1:1)	Not required	LIT-MS/MS	Not available	59
Thiabendazole	Peel of treated oranges	Paper spray (4 kV), methanol/water (9:1)	Not required (surface wiping)	Portable MS (ion trap)	Not available	60
Pyrazole fungicides: isopyrazam, fluxapyroxad, penflufen and pyraclostrobin	Spiked wines	Capillary paper spray (2.5 kV), methanol	Not required	QqQ-MS/MS	LOQs: 2 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for each analyte	61
Atrazine and propazine	Spiked tap water	Paper spray with wax- printed channels (4.5 kV), methanol/water (1 : 1)	Not required	Orbitrap-MS	LOD < 1.25 pmol	64
Acetochlor, alachlor, benzeneacetamide, butachlor, metolachlor, napropamid, pretilachlor	Spiked milk	Paper spray with silica- coated substrate, methanol/water (8:2)	Not required	QqQ-MS/MS	LOQs: 10.9 - 242.4 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	67
Herbicides: diuron, and 2,4- dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D)	apple, banana, and grape	Paper spray with MIP membrane substrate (3.5 kV), methanol (0.1% FA for positive ionization; 0.1% ammonium hydroxide for negative ionization)	Extraction with methanol	Q-Orbitrap- MS/MS	LLOQs: diuron, 0.41 – 0.99 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; 2,4-D, 1.02 - 2.0 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	68
Carbofuran, methyl parathion, parathion	Spiked orange surface (50 ppm)	Paper spray using paper coated with CNTs as substrate (3 V), methanol/water (1:1)	Not required (surface swabbing)	LIT-MS/MS	Not available	69

Atrazine, diuron and methomyl	Arugula, basil, cabbage, lettuce and kale vegetable samples	Paper spray with a paraffined microchannel (3.5 kV), methanol (0.1% FA)	Extraction with methanol	Q-Orbitrap-MS	LOQs: 4.12 – 83.33 ppb	65
Atrazine, diuron and methomyl	Arugula, basil, cabbage, lettuce and kale vegetable samples	Leaf spray (3.5 kV), methanol (0.1% FA)	Not required	Q-Orbitrap-MS	LOQs: 0.11 – 120 ppb	65
Acetamiprid, diphenylamine, imazalil, linuron, and thiabendazole	Peel and pulp of different fruits and vegetables	Leaf spray (3.5 kV), isopropyl alcohol	Not required	LIT-MS/MS	LODs : 5-50 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$	71
beta-Cypermethrin	Spiked apple juice	Wooden-tip ESI (3.5 kV), methanol (0.1% FA)	Not required	QTRAP-MS/MS	LOD: 30.0 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (30.0 pg)	73
PESI						
Glufosinate and glyphosate	Human serum	PESI (1.7 kV), ammonium formate (10 mM)/ethanol (1:1)	Dilution	QqQ-MS/MS	LOQs: 1560 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for both herbicides	76
Paraquat	Human serum	PESI (1.7 kV), ammonium formate (10 mM)/ethanol (1:1)	Dilution	QqQ-MS/MS	LCL: 15 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	77
Acephate, acetamiprid, clothianidin, thiophanate-methyl	Living plants	SF-PESI (2.5 kV), ACN/water (1:1) (0.1% FA)	Not required	TOF-MS	LOD of acetamiprid in methanol solution over Teflon substrate < 50 pg	78
TD-ESI						
8 fungicides, 12 insecticides, 2 herbicides	Fruits and vegetables	TD-ESI (4.5 kV), water (0.1% FA)/methanol (1:1)	Not required	QqQ-MS/MS	LOD: 0.5 - 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for aqueous pesticide standards	80
308 pesticides	Tomato and bell pepper	TD-ESI (4.5 kV), 5 mM NH_4OAc in 40% MeOH	Not required	QqQ-MS/MS	LOD < 50 ppb, for benthiazole standard solution	81
Acephate, chlorpyrifos, diazinon, dimethoate, iprobenfos, and methamidophos	Gastric juice	TD-ESI (3.5 - 4.5 kV), water/methanol (1:1) (0.1% acetic acid)	Not required	QqQ-MS/MS	LOD: 4.3 – 9.9 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	82
Chlorpyrifos, dimethoate, methamidophos, methomyl, paraquat	Human oral fluid	TD-ESI (3.5 - 4.5 kV), water/methanol (1:1) (0.1% acetic acid)	Sampling with a cotton swab and subsequent pesticide	QqQ-MS/MS	LODs: 1 – 10 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	83

extraction with
methanol

681 Abbreviations: ACN, acetonitrile; FA, formic acid; LCL, lowest calibration level; LIT, linear ion trap; LLE, liquid-liquid extraction; MS, mass spectrometry; QTRAP, hybrid
682 triple quadrupole/ion trap; QqQ, triple quadrupole; TOF, time-of-flight.

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Table 2 Summary of relevant methods for pesticides analysis by APCI-related ambient mass spectrometry.

Compounds	Matrix	Ambient ionization technique	Sample preparation	MS analysis	Analytical performance	Refs
DART						
Strobilurins fungicides: Azoxystrobin, dimoxystrobin, kresoxim-methyl, picoxystrobin, pyraclostrobin, trifloxystrobin	Wheat	DART, He; Confirmatory analysis: DESI, methanol/water (1:1) (0.1% formic acid)	DART-TOFMS: Extraction with ethyl acetate. DESI-MS/MS: Microextraction with a C18 pipet tip using methanol as extracting solvent	TOFMS	LOQs 5-30 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$	87
Dicyandiamide	Powdered milk	TM-DART using He as ionization gas	Extraction with acetonitrile/water (8:2)	Q-TOFMS	LOQ: 250 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$	88
50 pesticides (positive and negative ionization)	Red and white wine	TM-DART, He	Modified QuEChERS procedure	QqQ-MS/MS and TOFMS	(i) DART-QqQ MS/MS, LOQs 1-100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; (ii) DART-TOFMS, LOQs 25-250 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.	89
31 pesticides (positive ionization)	Red and white wine	TM-DART, He	Direct determination	QqQ-MS/MS and TOFMS	(i) DART-QqQ MS/MS, LOQs 25-500 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; (ii) DART-TOFMS, LOQs 100-500 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.	90
Amitrole, cyromazine, diethanolamine, melamine, propamocarb, 1,2,4-triazole, triethanolamine,	Lettuce and celery	DART using He as ionization gas	Modified QuPPE procedure	Orbitrap MS	LOQs 50 - 190 μgkg^{-1}	91

Thiram and ziram	Fruit	DART, He	Surface extraction with acetonitrile	TOFMS and OrbitrapMS	LOQs: (i) DART-TOF: 1000 and 500 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for thiram and ziram, respectively; and (ii) DART-Orbitrap: 100 and 1000 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for thiram and ziram, respectively.	41
132 pesticides	Surfaces of grapes, apples, and oranges	TM-DART using He as ionization gas	Sampling by foam swabs	Orbitrap MS	Using foam swabs: 86% target analytes detected at levels of 2 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (apple or orange) and 10 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (grape)	93
Mixtures of 240, 140, 132 and 60 pesticides	Surfaces of apples, kiwis, peaches and tomatoes	DART using He as ionization gas	Sampling by foam swabs	Orbitrap MS	More than 80% of target analytes were detected at levels of 2, 5 and 10 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$	94
164 pesticides	Surfaces of apples, oranges, and broccoli	TM-DART using He as ionization gas	Sampling by polyurethane foam disks	Q-Orbitrap MS	Spiked pesticides at concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ were 100% detected onto apples and oranges, and 80% onto broccoli	95
Dimethoate, malathion, methamidophos,	Surfaces of cherry tomatoes, oranges, peaches, and carrots	TM-DART using He as ionization gas	Sampling by two kinds of swabs: (i) cotton, and (ii) polyester	Orbitrap MS	Concentrations ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$): dimethoate (20 and 200), methamidophos (200), and malathion (80 and 800)	96
Ametryn, atrazine, prometon, prometryne, propazine, simazine,	Lake water and orange juice	DART using N_2 as ionization gas	IT-SPME	TOFMS	LOQs: 0.06 - 0.46 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	97
19 pesticides	Concord grape juice, orange juice, cow milk, and river water	TM-DART using He as ionization gas	SPME extraction performed onto the coated mesh	QqQ-MS/MS	LOQs, Concord grape juice and surface water (0.1-5 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$); orange juice (0.1-0.5 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$); cow milk (0.1-1 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	99
APGD						
Thiabendazole	Lemon skin	FAPA (pin-to-plate design), He gas flow, 0.8 L min^{-1} ; operating current, 25 mA	Surface rubbed with a polyester swab	TOFMS	Not available	101
10 pesticides	Spiked fruit juices and fruit peel (apple, cranberry, grape, orange, and salad leafs)	FAPA (pin-to-plate design), He; DC 0.5 kV, 40 mA	Fruit juices spotted on filter paper; pesticide solution spotted on fruit/vegetable surface	Q-TOF-MS/MS	LODs, (i) fruit juices, 1 - 500 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; (ii) apple skin, 0.01 - 5 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$	102

Ametryn, diphenylamine, ethoxyquin, isofenphosmethyl, isoproturon, malathion, parathion-ethyl, terbuthylazine	Standards	FAPA (pin-to-capillary design), He,	Not required	LIT-MS/MS	LODs: 0.004 - 9.2 fmol	103
Ametryn, amitraz, buprofezin, dimethoate, diphenylamine, imazalil, isoproturon, malathion, parathion-ethyl	Peels and extracts of apples, oranges, tomatoes, green peppers, grapes, and celery	MFGDP, He 0.6 L min ⁻¹ ; DC 820 V, 15 mA.	Two approaches: (i) QuEChERS, and (ii) direct determination on peel	IT-MS/MS	LODs, 0.13-3.09 µg kg ⁻¹ for fruit and vegetable extracts (QuEChERS)	105
Corona discharge						
Atrazine	Unripe pumpkin surface and cloths	DAPCI using ambient air as discharge gas	Not required	LIT-MS/MS	1-10 pg of atrazine detected	110
Dimethoate	Orange juices	TDCI using ionic liquid (1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide salt)	Not required	LIT-MS/MS	LOD 0.9 ng L ⁻¹	112
12 pesticides	Standards	DCBI source using He as discharge gas	Not required	Q-MS	LODs 1 - 9.6 ng	113
Acephate, isoprocarb, dimethoate, dichlorvos, and dicofol	Spiked water, river water, tap water, and wastewater	DCBI source using He as discharge gas	Microextraction in PDMS substrate		LODs of 1 µg L ⁻¹	114
Dicrotophos, pirimicarb, carbaryl, and triazophos	Standards	RTILs matrix-assisted DCBI, using He as discharge gas	Not required	Q-MS	LODs: 2 - 10 ng	115
DBD						
Prochloraz, propazine, spinosad	Standards	LD-DBDI, He 0.2 L min ⁻¹ ; AC, 20 kHz, 4.5 kV,	None	ITMS	Not available	123
Dichlorvos, diethyl ethylphosphonate, diisopropyl methylphosphonate, dimethyl	Standards	ACaPI, 1.6 kV, 5.75 kHz	None	Portable LIT-MS/MS	LODs: 1.0 – 6.3 µg L ⁻¹	124

methylphosphonate, diethyl phosphoramidate						
13 agrochemicals	Fruit peels, fruit/vegetable extracts and water	LTP, He 0.4 L min ⁻¹ ; AC, 2.5 kHz, 5-10 kV; 150 °C heated surface (except direct peel analysis)	Two approaches: i) direct determination on fruit peel or spiked water, and ii) QuEChERS extracts	LIT MS/MS	LODs QuEChERS extracts: pepper (0.4-200 µg kg ⁻¹); orange (0.4-20 µg kg ⁻¹); tomato (0.2-20 µg kg ⁻¹)	132
Acetamiprid, cyprodinil, fenhexamid, fludioxonil	Grapes and raspberries	LTP, He 0.3 L min ⁻¹ ; AC, 10 kV, 30 kHz; 150 °C heated substrate	QuEChERS (citrate buffer) extracts	Orbitrap MS	LOQs ranged from 1 to 70 µg kg ⁻¹	133
10 multiclass fungicides	Red wine	LTP, He 0.45 L min ⁻¹ ; AC, 6.2 kV, 2.5 kHz; 120 °C heated substrate	Dilution (1:5) with ACN	IT-MS/MS	LODs, ranged between 15 to 300 µg L ⁻¹	134
12 pesticides	Broomcorn	TD-LTP, He 0.15 L min ⁻¹ ; 180 °C for TD; 0.1 L min ⁻¹ air flow for sample transport.	Methanolic extraction in ultrasonic bath	QqQ MS	LODs ranged between 10 and 1000 µg L ⁻¹ .	135
Carbaryl, gramidicid S, imazalil, spinosad,	Standards	modified LTP, He 0.25 L min ⁻¹ ; desorption by ultrasonically vibrating blade	None	Orbitrap MS	LODs 0.1 – 100 ng	136
Diphenylamine	Apples	LTP (reduced size), He 0.3 L min ⁻¹ ; AC, 17 kV, 6 kHz;	None	LIT-MS/MS (portable)	--	60
11 pesticides	Standards	Handheld LTP, 7.4-V, 900 mAh Li-polymer battery; (i) Air, 0.1 L min ⁻¹ ; (ii) and (iii) He, 0.1 L min ⁻¹	None	(i) and (ii) LIT MS/MS; (iii) Mini MS	(i) LTP (air)-MS/MS, LODs 0.004-300 ng; (ii) LTP (He)-MS/MS, LODs 0.001-0.9 ng; (iii) LTP (He)-MS (mini), LODs 0.1-200 ng	137
Photoionization						
Aldicarb, carbofuran, ditalimfos, imazalil, methiocarb, methomyl,	Standards and orange peel	DAPPI using different solvents (acetone, toluene, and anisol) as spray solvent. For orange	Not required	IT-MS	LODs: 30-300 pg (0.14 to 1.4 pmol)	140

oxamyl, pirimicarb, thiabendazole		peel analysis, acetone was selected as spray solvent				
Acetamiprid, clothianidin, imidacloprid, thiacloprid, thiamethoxam	Standards and thiacloprid detection on fresh rose leaves and turnip rape flower	DAPPI using acetone as spray solvent	Not required	IT-MS	LODs: 0.1 – 1 µg L ⁻¹ (0.4-5.0 fmol) for standard analytes	¹⁴¹

686 IT, ion trap; IT-SPME, in-tube solid phase microextraction; LIT, linear ion trap; Q, single quadrupole; QqQ, triple quadrupole; Q-TOF, quadrupole time-of-flight;
687

688 **Figure Captions**

689 **Figure 1** Typical workflow of a routine pesticide testing method using chromatographic
690 techniques and the role ambient MS may play to speed up these procedures, allowing
691 even on-site sample analysis when portable MS instrumentation is used. Adapted from
692 Ref. [8] with permission from Elsevier.

693

694 **Figure 2.** Schematic representations of (a) DESI (Ref. [10]); (b) EESI (Ref. [45]); (c)
695 nanoEESI (Ref. [49]); (d) PESI (Ref. [74]); (e) PS-MS (Ref. [59]). For details, see text.
696 Adapted with permission from the publishers (Wiley, Royal Society of Chemistry, ACS
697 and .

698

699 **Figure 3.** Schematic diagram of the TD-ESI-MS analytical procedure. Adapted from ref.
700 [83], with permission from Wiley.

701

702 **Figure 4.** Schematic representations of (a) DART (Ref. [11]); (b) Sample holder and
703 upper view of TM-DART (Ref. [86]); (c) DBDI (pin-to-plate) (Ref. [121]); (d) LD-DBDI
704 (Ref. [123]); (e) ACaPI source (inner (I.E.) and outer electrodes (O.E.) are shown)
705 coupled to SPME desorption chamber (Ref. [128]); (f) LTP (Ref. [118]); (g) Ultrasonic-
706 assisted desorption DBDI-MS (Ref. [136]); (h) Pin-to-plate and pin-to-capillary
707 configurations of FAPA (Ref. [103]). For details, see text. Adapted with permission from
708 the publishers (ACS, Elsevier and Royal Society of Chemistry).

709

710 **Figure 5.** Schematic representations of: (a) DAPCI (Ref. [110]); (b) TDCI (Ref. [111]);
711 (c) DAPPI (Ref. [138]); (d) DCBI (Ref. 113). For details, see text. Adapted with
712 permission from the publishers (Wiley, Elsevier, Royal Society of Chemistry and ACS
713 respectively).

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- 1 USEPA. URL (<https://www.epa.gov/ingredients-used-pesticide-products/basic-information-about-pesticide-ingredients>) (last accessed: July 2020)
- 2 EU. URL (https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides_en) (last accessed: July 2020).
- 3 EEA (European Environment Agency). Environmental indicator report, 2018. URL (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/airs/2018/environment-and-health/pesticides-sales>) (last accessed: July 2020).
- 4 M. Farré and D. Barceló, Analysis of emerging contaminants in food, *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.*, 2013, **43**, 240-253.
- 5 E. Pose-Juan, M. J. Sánchez-Martín, M. S. Andrades, M. S. Rodríguez-Cruz and E. Herrero-Hernández, Pesticide residues in vineyard soils from Spain: Spatial and temporal distributions, *Sci. Tot. Environ.*, 2015, **514**, 351-358.
- 6 A.R. Fernández-Alba (ed.), *Chromatographic-Mass Spectrometric Food Analysis for Trace Determination of Pesticide Residues*, Comprehensive Analytical Chemistry vol. 43, Elsevier, 2004.
- 7 J. J. Villaverde, B. Sevilla-Morán, C. López-Goti, J. L. Alonso-Prados and P. Sandín-España, Trends in analysis of pesticide residues to fulfil the European Regulation (EC) No. 1107/2009, *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.*, 2016, **80**, 568-580.
- 8 A. Molina-Díaz, M. Beneito-Cambra, D. Moreno-González, B. Gilbert-López, Ambient mass spectrometry from the point of view of Green Analytical Chemistry, *Current Opinion in Green and Sustainable Chemistry*, 2019, **19**, 50-60.
- 9 R. G. Cooks, Z. Ouyang, Z. Takats and J. M. Wiseman, Ambient mass spectrometry, *Science*, 2006, **311**(5767), 1566-1570.
- 10 Z. Takáts, J. M. Wiseman, B. Gologan and R. G. Cooks, Mass spectrometry sampling under ambient conditions with desorption electrospray ionization, *Science*, 2004, **306**(5695), 471-473.
- 11 R. B. Cody, J.A. Laramée and H. D. Durst, Versatile new ion source for the analysis of materials in open air under ambient conditions, *Anal. Chem.*, 2005, **77**(8), 2297-2302.
- 12 R. Javanshad and A. R. Venter, Ambient ionization mass spectrometry: real-time, proximal sample processing and ionization, *Anal. Methods*, 2017, **9**(34), 4896-4907.
- 13 A. Venter, M. Nefliu and R. G. Cooks, Ambient desorption ionization mass spectrometry, *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.*, 2008, **27**(4), 284-290.
- 14 M. Z. Huang, C. H. Yuan, S. Y. Cheng, Y. T. Cho and J. Shiea, Ambient ionization mass spectrometry, *Annu. Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 2010, **3**, 43-65.
- 15 S. C. Cheng, C. Shiea, Y. L. Huang, C. H. Wang, Y. T. Cho and J. Shiea, Laser-based ambient mass spectrometry, *Anal. Methods*, 2017, **9**(34), 4924-4935.
- 16 P. Flanigan, R. Levis, Ambient Femtosecond Laser Vaporization and Nanosecond Laser Desorption Electrospray Ionization Mass Spectrometry, *Annual Review of Analytical Chemistry*, 2014, **7**, 229-256.
- 17 M. E. Monge, G. A. Harris, P. Dwivedi and F. M. Fernández, Mass spectrometry: Recent advances in direct open air surface sampling/ionization, *Chem. Rev.*, 2013, **113**(4), 2269-2308.
- 18 L.M.L. Nolet, B.K. Munjanja, *Ambient Mass Spectroscopy Techniques in Food and the environment*. CRC Press, 2019.
- 19 M-Z. Huang, C.-H. Yuan, S.-C- Chang, Y.-T. Cho, J. Shiea, Ambient ionization mass spectrometry, *Annual Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 2010, **3**, 43-65.
- 20 H. Chen, G. Gámez and R. Zenobi, What Can We Learn from Ambient Ionization Techniques? *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.*, 2009, **20**(11), 1947-1963.

-
- 21 D. J. Weston, Ambient ionization mass spectrometry: Current understanding of mechanistic theory; analytical performance and application areas, *Analyst*, 2010, **135**(4), 661-668.
 - 22 R. M. Alberici, R. C. Simas, G. B. Sanvido, W. Romão, P. M. Lalli, M. Benassi, I. B. S. Cunha and M. N. Eberlin, Ambient mass spectrometry: bringing MS into the “real world”, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2010, **398**(1), 265-294.
 - 23 M. Z. Huang, S. C. Cheng, Y. T. Cho and J. Shiea, Ambient ionization mass spectrometry: A tutorial, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2011, **702**(1), 1-15.
 - 24 G. A. Harris, A. S. Galhena and F. M. Fernández, Ambient sampling/ionization mass spectrometry: Applications and current trends, *Anal. Chem.*, 2011, **83**(12), 4508-4538.
 - 25 J. T. Shelley and G. M. Hieftje, Ambient mass spectrometry: Approaching the chemical analysis of things as they are, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 2011, **26**(11), 2153-2159.
 - 26 Z. Takats, J. M. Wiseman and R. G. Cooks, Ambient mass spectrometry using desorption electrospray ionization (DESI): Instrumentation, mechanisms and applications in forensics, chemistry, and biology, *J. Mass Spectrom.*, 2005, **40**(10), 1261-1275.
 - 27 D. R. Ifa, C. Wu, Z. Ouyang and R. G. Cooks, Desorption electrospray ionization and other ambient ionization methods: Current progress and preview, *Analyst*, 2010, **135**(4), 669-681.
 - 28 J. Chen, F. Tang, C. Guo, S. Zhang and X. Zhang, Plasma-based ambient mass spectrometry: a step forward to practical applications, *Anal. Methods*, 2017, **9**(34), 4908-4923.
 - 29 A. Albert, J. T. Shelley and C. Engelhard, Plasma-based ambient desorption/ionization mass spectrometry: State-of-the-art in qualitative and quantitative analysis, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2014, **406**(25), 6111-6127.
 - 30 X. L. Ding and Y. X. Duan, Plasma-based ambient mass spectrometry techniques: The current status and future prospective, *Mass Spectrom. Rev.*, 2015, **34**(4), 449-473.
 - 31 J. F. García-Reyes, B. Gilbert-López, A. Agüera, A. R. Fernández-Alba, and A. Molina-Díaz, in *Comprehensive Analytical Chemistry*, ed. A. R. Fernández-Alba, Elsevier, 58, 2012, chapter 8, 339-366.
 - 32 J. Hajslova, T. Cajka, L. Vaclavik, Challenging applications offered by direct analysis in real time (DART) in food-quality and safety analysis. *TrAC – Trends Anal. Chem.*, 2011, **30**(2), 204-218.
 - 33 DESI-MS, Waters web page, URL (https://www.waters.com/waters/en_US/DESI%3A-MS-Imaging-for-Biomedical-Research-/nav.htm?locale=en_US&cid=134988839), (Last accessed, July 2020)
 - 34 M.W.F. Nielen, H. Hooijerink, P. Zomer, J.G.J. Mol, Desorption electrospray ionization mass spectrometry in the analysis of chemical food contaminants in food, *TrAC – Trends Anal. Chem.*, 2011, **30**(2), 165-180.
 - 35 A. Gentili, S. Fanali, L.M. Rocca, Desorption electrospray ionization mass spectrometry for food analysis, *TrAC – Trends Anal. Chem.*, 2019, **115**, 162-173.
 - 36 J. F. García-Reyes, A. U. Jackson, A. Molina-Díaz and R. G. Cooks, Desorption electrospray ionization mass spectrometry for trace analysis of agrochemicals in food, *Anal. Chem.*, 2009, **81**(2), 820-829.
 - 37 S. Gerbig, G. Stern, H. E. Brunn, R. A. Düring, B. Spengler and S. Schulz, Method development towards qualitative and semi-quantitative analysis of multiple pesticides from food surfaces and extracts by desorption electrospray ionization mass

-
- spectrometry as a preseleive tool for food control, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2017, **409**(8), 2107-2117.
- 38 C. Berchtold, V. Müller, L. Meier, S. Schmid and R. Zenobi, Direct detection of chlorpropham on potato skin using desorption electrospray ionization, *J. Mass Spectrom.*, 2013, **48**(5), 587-593.
- 39 L. M. Rocca, J. Cecca, N. L'Episcopo and G. Fabrizi, Ambient mass spectrometry: Direct analysis of dimethoate, tebuconazole, and trifloxystrobin on olive and vine leaves by desorption electrospray ionization interface, *J. Mass Spectrom.*, 2017, **52**(11), 709-719.
- 40 X. Z. Zhang, C. J. Li, S. S. Chen, X. J. Li, H. Han and X. D. Ma, Direct Determination of atrazine residue on Chinese cabbage leaf using desorption electrospray ionization-tandem mass spectrometry and its application for diagnosing atrazine drift phytotoxicity, *J. AOAC Int.*, 2009, **92**(5), 1587-1592.
- 41 T. Cajka, K. Riddellova, P. Zomer, H. Mol and J. Hajslova, Direct analysis of dithiocarbamate fungicides in fruit by ambient mass spectrometry, *Food Addit. Contam.*, 2011, **28**(10), 1372-1382.
- 42 C. C. Mulligan, N. Talaty and R. G. Cooks, Desorption electrospray ionization with a portable mass spectrometer: *in situ* analysis of ambient surfaces, *Chem. Commun.*, 2006, **16**, 1709-1711.
- 43 L. Cardozo da Silva, I. Pereira, T. Colletes de Carvalho, J. F. Allochio Filho, W. Romão and B. Gontijo Vaz, Paper spray ionization and portable mass spectrometers: a review, *Anal. Methods*, 2019, **11**, 999-1013.
- 44 S. Gerbig, H. E. Brunn, B. Spengler and S. Schulz. Spatially resolved investigation of systemic and contact pesticides in plant material by desorption electrospray ionization mass spectrometry imaging (DESI-MSI), *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2015, **407**(24), 7379-7389.
- 45 H. Chen, A. Venter and R. G. Cooks, Extractive electrospray ionization for direct analysis of undiluted urine, milk and other complex mixtures without sample preparation, *Chem. Commun.*, 2006, **19**, 2042-2044.
- 46 Z. Zhou, M. Jin, J. Ding, Y. Zhou, J. Zheng, H. Chen, Rapid detection of atrazine and its metabolite in raw urine by extractive electrospray ionization mass spectrometry, *Metabolomics*, 2007, **3**(2), 101-104.
- 47 S. Wang, F. Li, Y. Liu, H. Zhao, H. Chen, High-throughput screening of toxic substances by extractive electrospray ionization mass spectrometry and their identification via databank construction, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2019, **411**, 4049–4054.
- 48 M. Li, B. Hu, J. Li, R. Chen, X. Zhang and H. Chen, Extractive electrospray ionization mass spectrometry toward *in situ* analysis without sample pretreatment, *Anal. Chem.*, 2009, **81**(18), 7724-7731.
- 49 H. Wang, J. Liu, R. G. Cooks and Z. Ouyang, Paper spray for direct analysis of complex mixtures using mass spectrometry, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2010, **49**(5), 877-880.
- 50 R. D. Espy, A. R. Muliadi, Z. Ouyang, R. G. Cooks, Spray mechanism in paper spray ionization, *Int. J. Mass Spectrom.*, 2012, **325–327**, 167–171.
- 51 E.M. McBride, P. M. Mach, E. S. Dhummakupt, S. Dowling, D. O. Carmany, P. S. Demond, G. Rizzo, N. E. Manicke, T. Glaros, Paper spray ionization: Applications and perspectives, *Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, 2019, **118**, 722-730.
- 52 VeriSpray, PaperSpray ion source, Thermoscientific, URL (<https://assets.thermofisher.com/TFS-Assets/CMD/brochures/br-65405-verispray-paper-spray-ion-source-br65405-en.pdf>) (Accessed July 2020)

-
- 53 S. L. Reeber, N. R. Wijeratne and M. L. Blackburn, Rapid measurement of agrochemicals by Paper Spray mass spectrometry (WP 303), poster of the 67th ASMS Conference on Mass Spectrometry and Allied Topics, Atlanta, Georgia, June 2-6, 2019.
- 54 S. Maher, F.P.M. Jjunju, D.E. Damon, H. Gorton, Y.S. Maher, S.U. Syed, R.M.A. Heeren, I.S. Young, S. Taylor, A.K. Badu-Tawiah, Direct analysis and quantification of metaldehyde in water using reactive paper spray mass spectrometry, *Sci. Rep-UK*, 2016, **6**, 35643.
- 55 S. L. Reeber, S. Gadi, S. B. Huang and G. L. Glish, Direct analysis of herbicides by paper spray ionization mass spectrometry, *Anal. Methods*, 2015, **7**(23), 9808-9816.
- 56 H. Evard, A. Kruve, R. Lõhmus and I. Leito, Paper spray ionization mass spectrometry: Study of a method for fast-screening analysis of pesticides in fruits and vegetables, *J. Food Compos. Anal.*, 2015, **41**, 221-225.
- 57 T. Guo, W. Yong and Y. Dong, Automatically high-throughput quantification by paper spray ionization mass spectrometry for multiple pesticides in wine, *Food Anal. Method*, 2019, **12**(5), 1208-1217.
- 58 A.C. Martins Moura, I. Neves Lago, C. Fernandes Cardoso, A. dos Reis Nascimento, I. Pereira, B. Gontijo Vaz, Rapid monitoring of pesticides in tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum L.*) during pre-harvest intervals by paper spray ionization mass spectrometry. *Food Chemistry*, 2020, **310**, 125938.
- 59 J. Liu, H. Wang, N. E. Manicke, J-M. Lin, R. G. Cooks and Z. Ouyang, Development, characterization, and application of paper spray ionization, *Anal. Chem.*, 2010, **82**(6), 2463-2471.
- 60 S. Soparawalla, F. K. Tadjimukhamedov, J. S. Wiley, Z. Ouyang and R. G. Cooks, In situ analysis of agrochemical residues on fruit using ambient ionization on a handheld mass spectrometer, *Analyst*, 2011, **136**(21), 4392-4396.
- 61 Y. Ren, S. Chiang, W. Zhang, X. Wang, Z. Lin, Z. Ouyang, Paper-capillary spray for direct mass spectrometry analysis of biofluid samples, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2016, **408**(5), 1385 - 1390.
- 62 F. Pu, W. Zhang, C. Han, Z. Ouyang, Fast quantitation of pyrazole fungicides in wine by ambient ionization mass spectrometry, *Anal. Methods*, 2017, **9**(34), 5058 - 5064.
- 63 I. Murray, G. Walker, M. S. Bereman, Improving the analytical performance and versatility of paper spray mass spectrometry via paper microfluidics, *Analyst*, 2016, **141**, 4065-4073.
- 64 T. C. Colletes, P. T. Garcia, R. B. Campanha, P. V. Abdelnur, W. Romão, W. K. T. Coltro and B. G. Vaz, A new insert sample approach to paper spray mass spectrometry: a paper substrate with paraffin barriers, *Analyst*, 2016, **141**(5), 1707-1713
- 65 I. Pereira, S. R. M. Rodrigues, T. C. de Carvalho, V. V. Carvalho, G. S. Lobón, J. F. P. Bassane, E. Domingos, W. Romão, R. Augusti and B. G. Vaz, Rapid screening of agrochemicals by paper spray ionization and leaf spray mass spectrometry: which technique is more appropriate?, *Anal. Methods*, 2016, **8**(31), 6023-6029.
- 66 J. Liu, Y. He, S. Chen, M. Ma, S. Yao, B. Chen, New urea-modified paper substrate for enhanced analytical performance of negative ion mode paper spray mass spectrometry, *Talanta*, 2017, **166**, 306-314.
- 67 Q. Wang, Y. Zheng, X. Zhang, X. Han, T. Wang, Z. Zhang, A silica coated paper substrate: development and its application in paper spray mass spectrometry for rapid analysis of pesticides in milk, *Analyst*, 2015, **140**, 8048-8056.
- 68 I. Pereira, M. Ferreira Rodrigues, A. Rodrigues Chaves, B. Gontijo Vaz, Molecularly imprinted polymer (MIP) membrane assisted direct spray ionization mass

-
- spectrometry for agrochemicals screening in foodstuffs, *Talanta*, 2018, **178**, 507 - 514.
- 69 R. Narayanan, D. Sarkar, R. G. Cooks, T. Pradeep, Molecular Ionization from Carbon Nanotube Paper, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2014, **53**, 5936–5940.
- 70 J. Liu, H. Wang, R. G. Cooks, Z. Ouyang, Leaf spray: Direct chemical analysis of plant material and living plants by mass spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.* 2011, **83**(20), 7608 - 7613.
- 71 N. Malaj, Z. Ouyang, G. Sindona and R. G. Cooks, Analysis of pesticide residues by leaf spray mass spectrometry, *Anal. Methods*, 2012, **4**(7), 1913-1919.
- 72 B. Hu, P. K. So, H. Chen and Z. P. Yao, Electrospray ionization using wooden tips, *Anal. Chem.*, 2011, **83**(21), 8201-8207.
- 73 B. C. Yang, F. Wang, W. Deng, Y. Zou, F. Y. Liu, X. D. Wan, X. Yang, H. Liu and O. P. Huang, Wooden-tip electrospray ionization mass spectrometry for trace analysis of toxic and hazardous compounds in food samples, *Anal. Methods*, 2015, **7**(14), 5886-5890.
- 74 K. Hiraoka, K. Nishidate, K. Mori, D. Asakawa and S. Suzuki, Development of probe electrospray using a solid needle, *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.*, 2007, **21**(18), 3139-3144.
- 75 Brochure of DPiMS-8060 ionization source, Shimadzu website, URL (https://www.shimadzu.com/an/pdf/60_c146e369.pdf) (Last accessed, July 2020)
- 76 K. Usui, E. Minami, Y. Fujita, E. Kubota, H. Kobayashi, T. Hanazawa, T. Yoshizawa, Y. Kamijo, M. Funayama, Application of probe electrospray ionization-tandem mass spectrometry to ultra-rapid determination of glufosinate and glyphosate in human serum, *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*, 2019, **174**, 175–181.
- 77 K. Usui, E. Minami, Y. Fujita, H. Kobayashi, T. Hanazawa, Y. Kamijo, M. Funayama, A fast paraquat quantitation method in human serum using probe electrospray ionization–tandem mass spectrometry for emergency settings, *Journal of Pharmacological and Toxicological Methods*, 2019, **100**, 106610.
- 78 M. K. Mandal, T. Ozawa, S. Saha, Md. M. Rahman, M. Iwasa, Y. Shida, H. Nonami and K. Hiraoka, Development of sheath-flow probe electrospray ionization mass spectrometry and its application to real time pesticide analysis, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 2013, **61**(33), 7889-7895.
- 79 M. Z. Huang, C. C. Zhou, D. L. Liu, S. S. Jhang, S. C. Cheng and J. Shiea, Rapid characterization of chemical compounds in liquid and solid states using thermal desorption electrospray ionization mass spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.*, 2013, **85**(19), 8956-8963.
- 80 C. Shiea, Y. L. Huang, D. L. Liu, C. C. Chou, J. H. Chou, P. Y. Chen, J. Shiea and M. Z. Huang, Rapid screening of residual pesticides on fruits and vegetables using thermal desorption electrospray ionization mass spectrometry, *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.*, 2015, **29**(2), 163-170.
- 81 S.-C. Cheng, R.-H. Lee, J.-Y. Jeng, C.-W. Lee, J. Shiea, Fast screening of trace multiresidue pesticides on fruit and vegetable surfaces using ambient ionization tandem mass spectrometry, *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 2020, **1102**, 63-71.
- 82 C.-W. Lee, H. Su, R.-H. Lee, Y.-P. Ling, Y.-D. Tsai, D.-C. Wu, J. Shiea, Point-of-care identification of organophosphates in gastric juice by ambient mass spectrometry in emergency settings, *Clinica Chimica Acta*, 2018, **485**, 288–297.
- 83 C. W. Lee, H. Su, P. Y. Chen, S. J. Lin, J. Shiea, S. J. Shin and B. H. Chen, Rapid identification of pesticides in human oral fluid for emergency management by

-
- thermal desorption electrospray ionization/mass spectrometry, *J. Mass Spectrom.*, 2016, **51**(2), 97-104.
- 84 J.H. Gross, Direct analysis in real time—a critical review on DART-MS, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2014, **406**, 63-80.
- 85 C. Tendero, C. Tixier, P. Tristant, J. Desmaison, P. Leprince, Atmospheric pressure plasmas: A review, *Spectrochimica Acta Part B*, 2006, **61**, 2-30.
- 86 J. J. Pérez, G. A. Harris, J. E. Chipuk, J. S. Brodbelt, M. D. Green, C. Y. Hampton and F. M. Fernández. Transmission-mode direct analysis in real time and desorption electrospray ionization mass spectrometry of insecticide-treated bednets for malaria control *Analyst*, 2010, **135**(4), 712-719.
- 87 J. Schurek, L. Vaclavik, H. Hooijerink, O. Lacina, J. Poustka, M. Sharman, M. Caldow, M. W. F. Nielen and J. Hajslova, Control of strobilurin fungicides in wheat using direct analysis in real time accurate time-of-flight and desorption electrospray ionization linear ion trap mass spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.*, 2008, **80**(24), 9567-9575.
- 88 L. Zhang, W. Yong, J. Liu, S. Wang, Q. Chen, T. Guo, J. Zhang, T. Tan, H. Su and Y. Dong, Determination of dicyandiamide in powdered milk using direct analysis in real time quadrupole time-of-flight tandem mass spectrometry, *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.*, 2015, **26**(8), 1414-1422.
- 89 T Guo, P. Fang, J. Jiang, F. Zhang, W. Yong, J. Liu and Y. Dong, Rapid screening and quantification of residual pesticides and illegal adulterants in red wine by direct analysis in real time mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A*, 2016, **1471**, 27-33.
- 90 W. Yong, T. Guo, P. Fang, J. Liu, Y. Dong, F. Zhang, Direct determination of multi-pesticides in wine by ambient mass spectrometry, *Int. J. Mass Spectrom.*, 2017, **417**, 53 - 57.
- 91 F. J. Lara, D. Chan, M. Dickinson, A. S. Lloyd, S. J. Adams, Evaluation of direct analysis in real time for the determination of highly polar pesticides in lettuce and celery using modified Quick Polar Pesticides Extraction method, *J. Chromatogr. A*, 2017, **1496**, 37 - 44.
- 92 M. Anastassiades, D. I. Kolberg, A. Benkenstein, E. Eichhorn, S. Zechmann, D.Mack, C. Wildgrube, I. Sigalov, D. Dörk, A. Barth, Quick method for the analysis of numerous highly polar pesticides in foods of plant origin via LC-MS/MS involving simultaneous extraction with methanol (QuPPE-method), http://www.crl-pesticides.eu/library/docs/srm/meth_QuPPE.pdf (Accessed July 2020).
- 93 S. E. Edison, L. A. Lin, B. M. Gamble, J. Wong and K. Zhang, Surface swabbing technique for the rapid screening for pesticides using ambient pressure desorption ionization with high-resolution mass spectrometry, *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.*, 2011, **25**(1), 127-139.
- 94 S. E. Edison, L. A. Lin and L. Parrales, Practical considerations for the rapid screening for pesticides using ambient pressure desorption ionisation with high-resolution mass spectrometry, *Food Addit. Contam.*, 2011, **28**(10), 1393-1404.
- 95 S. E. Kern, L. A. Lin and F. L. Fricke, Accurate mass fragment library for rapid analysis of pesticides on produce using ambient pressure desorption ionization with high-resolution mass spectrometry, *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.*, 2014, **25**(8), 1482-1488.
- 96 E. Crawford and B. Musselman, Evaluating a direct swabbing method for screening pesticides on fruit and vegetable surfaces using direct analysis in real time (DART) coupled to an Exactive benchtop orbitrap mass spectrometer, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2012, **403**(10), 2807-2812.
- 97 X. Wang, X. Li, Z. Li, Y. Zhang, Y. Bai and H. Liu, Online coupling of in-tube solid-phase microextraction with direct analysis in real time mass spectrometry for rapid

-
- determination of triazine herbicides in water using carbon-nanotubes-incorporated polymer monolith, *Anal. Chem.*, 2014, **86**(10), 4739-4747.
- 98 G. A. Gómez-Ríos, J. Pawliszyn, Solid phase microextraction (SPME)-transmission mode (TM) pushes down detection limits in direct analysis in real time (DART), *Chem. Commun.*, 2014, **50**(85), 12937 - 12940.
- 99 G. A. Gómez-Ríos, E. Gionfriddo, J. Poole, J. Pawliszyn, Ultrafast screening and quantitation of pesticides in food and environmental matrices by solid-phase microextraction-transmission mode (SPME-TM) and direct analysis in real time (DART), *Anal. Chem.* 2017, **89**(13), 7240 - 7248.
- 100 F. J. Andrade, J. T. Shelley, W. C. Wetzel, M. R. Webb, G. Gamez, S. J. Ray and G. M. Hieftje, Atmospheric pressure chemical ionization source. 1. Ionization of compounds in the gas phase, *Anal. Chem.*, 2008, **80**(8), 2646-2653.
- 101 F. J. Andrade, J. T. Shelley, W. C. Wetzel, M. R. Webb, G. Gamez, S. J. Ray and G. M. Hieftje, Atmospheric pressure chemical ionization source. 2. Desorption-ionization for the direct analysis of solid compounds, *Anal. Chem.*, 2008, **80**(8), 2654-2663.
- 102 M. C. Jecklin, G. Gamez, D. Touboul and R. Zenobi, Atmospheric pressure glow discharge desorption mass spectrometry for rapid screening of pesticides in food, *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.*, 2008, **22**(18), 2791-2798.
- 103 J. T. Shelley, J. S. Wiley and G. M. Hieftje, Ultrasensitive ambient mass spectrometric analysis with a pin-to-capillary flowing atmospheric-pressure afterglow source, *Anal. Chem.*, 2011, **83**(14), 5741-5748.
- 104 X. Ding, X. Zhan, X. Yuan, Z. Zhao and Y. Duan, Microfabricated glow discharge plasma (MFGDP) for ambient desorption/ionization mass spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.*, 2013, **85**(19), 9013-9020.
- 105 B. Wang, X. Ding, Z. Zhao and Y. Duan, Method development for directly screening pesticide residues in foodstuffs using ambient microfabricated glow discharge plasma (MFGDP) desorption/ionization mass spectrometry, *Int. J. Mass Spectrom.*, 2015, **377**, 507-514.
- 106 H. W. Chen, J. H. Lai, Y. F. Zhou, Y. F. Huan, J. Q. Li, X. Zhang, Z. C. Wang, M. B. Luo. Instrumentation and characterization of surface desorption atmospheric pressure chemical ionization mass spectrometry, *Chin. J. Anal. Chem.*, 2007, **35**(8), 1233-1240.
- 107 Z. Takats, I. Cotte-Rodriguez, N. Talaty, H. W. Chen and R. G. Cooks, Direct, trace level detection of explosives on ambient surfaces by desorption electrospray ionization mass spectrometry, *Chem. Commun.*, 2005, **15**, 1950-1952.
- 108 J. P. Williams, V. J. Patel, R. Holland and J.H. Scrivens, The use of recently described ionisation techniques for the rapid analysis of some common drugs and samples of biological origin, *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.*, 2006, **20**(9), 1447-1456.
- 109 J. P. Williams and J. H. Scrivens, Rapid accurate mass desorption electrospray ionisation tandem mass spectrometry of pharmaceutical samples, *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.*, 2005, **19**(24), 3643-3650.
- 110 H. Chen, J. Zheng, X. Zhang, M. Luo, Z. Wang and X. Qiao, Surface desorption atmospheric pressure chemical ionization mass spectrometry for direct ambient sample analysis without toxic chemical contamination, *J. Mass Spectrom.*, 2007, **42**(8), 1045-1056.
- 111 J. Han, J. Q. Li, X. Zhang, B. Hu, M. B. Luo and H. W. Chen, Development of thermal dissociation atmospheric chemical ionization source for rapid mass

-
- spectrometry analysis of ambient samples, *Chin. J. Anal. Chem.*, 2011, **39**(2), 288-292.
- 112 Y. Ouyang, X. Zhang, J. Han, X. Guo, Z. Zhu, H. Chen and L. Luo, Thermal dissociation atmospheric chemical ionization ion trap mass spectrometry with a miniature source for selective trace detection of dimethoate in fruit juices, *Analyst*, 2013, **138**(2), 472-479.
- 113 H. Wang, W. Sun, J. Zhang, X. Yang, T. Lin and L. Ding, Desorption corona beam ionization source for mass spectrometry, *Analyst*, 2010, **135**(4), 688-695.
- 114 X. Li, H. Wang, W. Sun and L. Ding, Desorption corona beam ionization coupled with a poly(dimethylsiloxane) substrate: Broadening the application of ambient ionization for water samples, *Anal. Chem.*, 2010, **82**(22), 9188-9193.
- 115 H. Wang, Y. Wu, B. Guo, W. Sun, L. Ding and B. Chen, Quantification of low-polar small molecules using room temperature ionic liquids matrix-assisted desorption corona beam ionization, *Analyst*, 2012, **137**(17), 3982-3988.
- 116 V. Horvatic, C. Vadla and J. Franzke, Discussion of fundamental processes in dielectric barrier discharges used for soft ionization, *Spectrochimica Acta Part B*, 2014, **100**, 52-61.
- 117 S. Brandt, F.D. Klute, A. Schütz, J. Franzke. Dielectric barrier discharges applied for soft ionization and their mechanism, *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 2017, **951**, 16-31.
- 118 J. D. Harper, N. A. Charipar, C. C. Mulligan, X. Zhang, R. G. Cooks and Z. Ouyang, Low-temperature plasma probe for ambient desorption ionization, *Anal. Chem.*, 2008, **80**(23), 9097-9104.
- 119 A. Michels, S. Tombrink, W. Vautz, M. Miclea, J. Franzke, Spectroscopic characterization of a microplasma used as ionization source for ion mobility spectrometry, *Spectrochimica Acta Part B*, 2007, **62**, 1208-1215.
- 120 H. Hayen, A. Michels, J. Franzke, Dielectric Barrier Discharge Ionization for Liquid Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.*, 2009, **81**, 10239-10245.
- 121 N. Na, M. Zhao, S. Zhang, C. Yang and X. Zhang, Development of a dielectric barrier discharge ion source for ambient mass spectrometry, *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.*, 2007, **18**(10), 1859-1862.
- 122 A. Michels, S. Tombrink, W. Vautz, M. Miclea, J. Franzke. Spectroscopic characterization of a microplasma used as ionization source for ion mobility spectrometry. *Spectrochim. Acta Part B.*, 2007, **62** (11), 1208-1215.
- 123 B. Gilbert-López, M. Schilling, N. Ahlmann, A. Michels, H. Hayen, A. Molina-Díaz, J. F. García-Reyes and J. Franzke, Ambient diode laser desorption dielectric barrier discharge ionization mass spectrometry of nonvolatile chemicals, *Anal. Chem.*, 2013, **85**(6), 3174-3182.
- 124 M. M. Nudnova, L. Zhu, R. Zenobi, Active capillary plasma source for ambient mass spectrometry, *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.* 2012, **26**, 1447-1452.
- 125 Plasmion GmbH website (URL: <https://www.plasmion.de>) (Last accessed: July 2020).
- 126 M. Mirabelli, J.C. Wolf, R. Zenobi. Pesticide analysis at ppt concentration levels: coupling nano-liquid chromatography with dielectric barrier discharge ionization-mass spectrometry. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2016, **408**, 3425-3434.
127. J.C. Wolf, R. Etter, M. Schaer, P. Siegenthaler, R. Zenobi. Direct and Sensitive Detection of CWA Simulants by Active Capillary Plasma Ionization coupled to a handheld Ion trap mass spectrometer. *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.* 2016, **27**, 1197-1202.
- 128 M. F. Mirabelli, E. Gionfriddo, J. Pawliszyn, R. Zenobi, A quantitative approach for pesticide analysis in grape juice by direct interfacing of a matrix compatible SPME

-
- phase to dielectric barrier discharge ionization-mass spectrometry, *Analyst*, 2018, 143, 891–899.
- 129 F.D. Klute, S. Brandt, P. Vogel, B. Biskup, C. Reininger, V. Horvatic, C. Vadla, P.B. Farnsworth, J. Franzke. Systematic Comparison between Half and Full Dielectric Barrier Discharges Based on the Low Temperature Plasma Probe (LTP) and Dielectric Barrier Discharge for Soft Ionization (DBDI) Configurations. *Anal. Chem.* 89 2017, 89, 9368-9374.
- 130 S. E. Spencer, B. G. Santiago, G. L. Glish, Miniature Flow-Through Low-Temperature Plasma Ionization Source for Ambient Ionization of Gases and Aerosols, *Anal. Chem.*, 2015, **87**, 11887-11892.
- 131 S. Martínez-Jarquín, A. Moreno-Pedraza, H. Guillén-Alonso, R. Winkler, Template for 3D Printing a Low-Temperature Plasma Probe, *Anal. Chem.*, 2016, **88**, 6976–6980.
- 132 J. S. Wiley, J. F. García-Reyes, J. D. Harper, N. A. Charipar, Z. Ouyang and R. G. Cooks, Screening of agrochemicals in foodstuffs using low-temperature plasma (LTP) ambient ionization mass spectrometry, *Analyst*, 2010, **135**(5), 971-979.
- 133 A. Albert, A. Kramer, S. Scheeren and C. Engelhard, Rapid and quantitative analysis of pesticides in fruits by QuEChERS pretreatment and low temperature plasma desorption/ionization orbitrap mass spectrometry, *Anal. Methods*, 2014, **6**(15), 5463-5471.
- 134 M. Beneito-Cambra, P. Pérez-Ortega, A. Molina-Díaz, J. F. García-Reyes, Rapid determination of multiclass fungicides in wine by low-temperature plasma (LTP) ambient ionization mass spectrometry, *Anal. Methods*, 2015, **7**(17), 7345-7351.
- 135 S. Wang, Z. Wang, K. Y. Hou and H. Y. Li, Thermal desorption low temperature plasma ionization mass spectrometry for rapid and sensitive detection of pesticides in broomcorn, *Chin. J. Anal. Chem.*, 2017, **45**(2), 175-182.
- 136 D. T. Usmanov, K. Hiraoka, H. Wada, S. Morita and H. Nonami, Desorption of low-volatility compounds induced by dynamic friction between microdroplets and an ultrasonically vibrating blade, *Analyst*, 2016, **141**(4), 1398-1404.
- 137 J. S. Wiley, J. T. Shelley and R. G. Cooks, Handheld low-temperature plasma probe for portable “Point-and-Shoot” ambient ionization mass spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.*, 2013, **85**(14), 6545-6552.
- 138 M. Haapala, J. Pól, V. Saarela, V. Arvola, T. Kotiaho, R. A. Ketola, S. Franssila, T. J. Kauppila and R. Kostianen, Desorption atmospheric pressure photoionization, *Anal. Chem.*, 2007, **79**(20), 7867-7872.
- 139 T. J. Kauppila and R. Kostianen, Ambient mass spectrometry in the analysis of compounds of low polarity, *Anal. Methods*, 2017, **9**(34), 4936-4953.
- 140 L. Luosujärvi, S. Kanerva, V. Saarela, S. Franssila, R. Kostianen, T. Kotiaho and T. J. Kauppila, Environmental and food analysis by desorption atmospheric pressure photoionization-mass spectrometry, *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.*, 2010, **24**(9), 1343-1350.
- 141 A. Vaikkinen, H. S. Schmidt, I. Kiiski, S. Rämö, K. Hakala, M. Haapala, R. Kostianen and T. J. Kauppila, Analysis of neonicotinoids from plant material by desorption atmospheric pressure photoionization-mass spectrometry, *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.* 2015, **29**(5), 424-430.
- 142 J.T. Shelley, S.J. Ray, and G.M. Hieftje, Laser ablation coupled to a flowing atmospheric pressure afterglow for ambient mass spectral imaging, *Anal. Chem.*, 2008, **80**(21), 8308–8313.
- 143 A. Moreno-Pedraza, I. Rosas-Román, N.S. Garcia-Rojas, H. Guillén-Alonso, C. Ovando-Vázquez, D. Díaz-Ramírez, J. Cuevas-Contreras, F. Vergara, N. Marsch-

Martínez, J. Molina-Torres, R. Winkler, Elucidating the distribution of plant metabolites from native tissues with laser desorption low-temperature plasma mass spectrometry imaging, *Anal. Chem.*, 2019, **91**(4), 2734–2743.

¹⁴⁴ J.T. Shelley, and G.M. Hieftje, Ionization matrix effects in plasma-based ambient mass spectrometry sources, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 2010, **25**, 345–350.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

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